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[description of manuscript]

Title	Rasendramaṅgala
Commentary	[title of commentary]
Author	Nāgārjuna Siddha
Commentator	[commentator]
Rubric	(folio 1v1) śrīvardhamānājineśvarāya namaḥ śrīgurubhyo namaḥ
Incipit	(folio 1v1) natvā surendraṃ śivasaukhyadāyakaṃ kārakaṃ apārasaṃsārasamudratāraṃ
Explicit	(folio 24v) śrīr astuḥ kalyāṇam astuḥ śubhaṃ bhavatuḥ śreyo stuḥ sakalasaṃjanasya śrīr astuḥ
Physical description	
Language/Script	[Sanskrit in Devanāgarī script.]
Format	pothi
Material	paper
Extent	999 folios.
Dimensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (leaf) [height] x [width] cm • (written) [height] x [width] cm
Foliation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • () Scribal foliation 1-25. • () Modern numerals written in pencil, centre-right margin, recto and verso.
Condition	[whether the manuscript is complete, description of wear and damage]
Layout	[description of marginal frame lines, etc.]

Hand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (sole) Devanāgarī script in black ink. • (major) Devanāgarī script in red ink. • (minor) English script in green highlighter.
Additions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marginal annotations and corrections throughout. • Marginal illustration of alchemical apparatus on leaf 2r, and 27 fuller illustrations on leaves 24v-25v.
Binding	[description of cover, binding, and/or stringholes]
History	
Date of production	Vikrama Saṃvat 1737 (AD 1681).
Place of origin	[place of production]
Provenance	[record of ownership]
Acquisition	[how it was acquired]

01

śrīśailaparvatastho'sau siddho nāgārjuno mahān||
sarvasattvopakāri ca sarvabhogaguṇānvitaḥ| |

Pa: śrīśailaḥ pa° A1, Ko1: śrīśailaparvatasthā-
sau B: śrīśailaparvatasthō J1: śrīśailyapa-
rva₁ tasthāsau Ko2: śrīśailaparvatasyo₁ sau
L: śrīśailyaparvatasthā'sau P: śrīśailyaparvata-
stho sau R: °tasthāyī A2, U: °stho sau
U: si|ddo B: nāgārjutō Ko2: nāgārjūno L: nā-
garjuno B: nahān||2g| Ko2: mähānḥ U: sarva
copa° P: sarbasattropa° A1, Ko1: sarvasattro-
pa° L: sarvasatropakāri Ko2: °kāri A1, Ko1, L,
P: om J1: syāt P: sarbabhogāgu° L: sarvalogā-
gu° J1, Ko1: sarvabhogāgu° B: sarvvasā-
dhugu° A1: ____bhogāgu° R: sarvabhāgyasa-
māLnvataḥ Ko2: °gagūṇānvita 1

02

prārthito dadhate śīghraṃ yasya yasya hi yādṛśaṃ||
dṛṣtvā tyāgaṃ ca bhogaṃ ca sūtakasya prasādataḥ| |

Ko1: prārthitau Ko2: prārthanād Pa: pārthito
U: prārthanā A2: dadane B, G, Ko2, R: dadatē
J1: śīghra Ko2: śīghraṃḥ B: tato R: tenā
A1: om A2: ya sṣa sya G: kasya Ko2, U: yasyā
R: paśya J1: add ya J1: om yā°
Ko2: yādṛśaṃḥ U: yā₁ Ldrṛśaṃ|| A1: dṛṣtvāṃ
G: draṣtvā U: dṛṣtvo A2, B: om L: vyāgaṃ A1,
J1, Ko1, L, P: om Ko1: bhoge₁ Ko2: om
Pa: caṃ A1, Ko1, L, P: sūtakasya Ko2: sutaka-
syaḥ Ko2: prabhāvena U: prabhāvataḥ||
Ko2: add tathaiva ca 2

03

sarvasattvamahābodhī sūrasenas tathaiva ca||
teṣāṃ madhye pradhānaṃ ca ratnaghoṣaprabhākaraḥ| |

A2 P: sarbasattvamahāvedhī Ko2: °tvamāhā-
be₁2₁ dhiḥ B: °mayā bōdhī R: °mayo vedhī A1,
Ko1, L, Pa: °hāvedhī J1: °hāvidhī R: svara°
A1: sūtas J1, Ko1, L, P: sūtasena Ko2: sūra-
nasva U: sūranas Pa: bhūrasanatadhevahi
A1: add tena U: tata° J1, L, P: taveva Ko1: ta-
vaiva A1, J1, Ko1, L, P: hi Ko2: caḥ Pa: om
Ko2: teṣyāṃ J1: madhya Ko2: madhe R: ma-
dhyo U: madhyaṃ A1, J1: prallotaś G: pra-
dhānaś Ko1, L, P: prallātaś Pa: pradhonaś
R: pradānaṃ Ko2: caḥ Pa: ca₁ra° B, G, U: ra-
tnaghoṣo pra° Ko2: ratnaghosoprabhākara 3
A1, J1, L: °ṣa prabhākaraḥ R: °pratārakaḥ

04

kṛtāñjalipuṭo bhūtvā nāgārjunapurasthitaḥ||
pṛcchate rasakarmāṇi vidyādānaṃ dadasva me| |

J1: kvatām° Ko2: kṛtāmjalipuṭo B: °li puvyê
G: °li vuṭo B, U: nāgārjuna pu° A1, Ko1, L: nā-
gārjunoparisthitaḥ G: nāgārjunapurasthitaḥ
J1, P, Pa: nāgārjuno paristhitaḥ A2: °na pu-
nasthitaḥ||L Ko2: °rasthitaḥ J1: pṛchati
Ko1: pṛcchate R: pṛschate U: prachate
Ko2: rasyaka° R: rasakanyāṇi G: vidyā dānaṃ
J1: vidyādīnaṃ Ko2: vidyādānaṃ

śrīnāgārjunovāca

A1, Ko2: nāgārjuno vāca A2: śrīnāgārjuna
uvāca B: nāgārjuna uvāca| | | G: śrīnāgārjuna
uvāca| | J1, P: nāgārjunovāca Ko1: nāgārju-
novāca, L: nāgārjunovāca| Pa: nāgārju-
nauvāLca|" R: śrī nāgārjuna uvāca U: |śrīnāgā-
rjunovāca|

05

sādhu sādhu mahāprājña tuṣṭo'haṃ bhaktivatsalaḥ||
kathayāmi na sandeho yat tvayā paripṛchitam||

A1: om J1: sādhuṃ B: sāL B: karmmahā°
G: mahāmprājña J1, U: mahāprājñaḥ
Ko2: mahābhāgaḥ Pa: mahāprājña | R: mahā-
mnājña G, Ko1, Ko2, P: tuṣṭo haṃ
Pa: tuṣṭhoḥ B: sakti° A2: bhaktivatsala
Ko2: bhaktivachalaḥ R: °tsala G: tatha° Ko1,
P: ni Pa: niḥsaṃ° A1, J1, L: nisaṃ°
A2: saṃdehaṃ R: mandeho G: yo Ko1, U: ya
A1, A2, B, Ko2, L, Pa: yatvayā J1: yatvāyā
G: yatvayā G: add sya A1, J1: paripṛchati
A2: paripṛṣṭitaṃ 5 9 8 R: paripṛchayatām
U: °chitaḥ||

06

valīpalitanāśaṃ ca tathā kālasya vañcanaṃ||
yathā lohe tathā dehe kramate nātra saṃśayaḥ *

A2: ijīpa° A1, Ko1, P, U: valīpa° L: valpili°
B: valīpalitavināśaṃ Ko2: valīpalivī, nāsaṃ
Pa: valīpalitamāśaṃ J1: om Ko2: caḥ A1,
Ko1, L: add kāmaṃ yathā P: add kā.....maṃ
P: yathākā° A1: kāmlasya U: kāyasya
A1: taṃcanaṃ Ko1, L: taṃvanaṃ
Ko2: vaṃcanaṃḥ P: tavanaṃ R: vāṃcanaṃ
Ko2: loheṃ U: lohaṃ A1, B: tatha A1: dihe
R: kṣamate G: kramatenā ca A2: mānātra
Ko1: śaṃśayaḥ Ko2: saṃśaya 6

Parallels

07

sahasrāyutalakṣaṃ ca koṭivedhī bhaved rasaḥ||
tad ahaṃ saṃpravakṣyāmi sādhanam ca yathāvidhi||

A2 L: sahasroyu° G: sahasāyu° A1, J1: sahsrā-
yu° Ko2: sahastrayūta° B: sahsrāyutalakṣa
R: sahasrāsavalatvaṃ Ko1: tva Ko2: caḥ
G: koṭī vedhī Ko2: koṭivedhi G: bhavend
Ko2: ṛsaḥ Ko2, Pa: tadahaṃ B, R: saṃpra-
vakṣāmi Ko2: saṃpravakṣāmīḥ R: bhavato
Ko2: sādhanamca A1, U: om R: hi B, U: ya-
thāvidhiḥ G: yathā vidhiḥ | Ko2: yathāvidhī 7

08

satvānām bodhanārthāya sādhitā vaṭayakṣaṇī||
dvādaśāni ca varṣāṇi mahākleśaḥ kṛto mayā |

U: śodha° Pa: om bodha° R: bhojanā°
B: bhoru nā° A1, J1, P: bodhinā° Ko1: bodhi-
nāthāya L: bodhināthāpa Ko2: °rthā, vya
J1: sādhayitva Ko2: vaṭayakṣaṇiḥ G: add
mayā Ko1: dvādaśva, ni Ko2: dvādasāmṇi
P: dvādaśava, ni L: dvādaśa A2: dvādaśanava-
va° G: dvādaśava° A1, J1: dvādaśavanivasa-
rvāṇi Ko1: va Ko2, P: om R: tu B: karṣāṇi
Ko1, P: sarvāṇi Ko2: varṣāmṇi L: add sarvāṇi
A1: mahākṛteśaḥ B, J1: mahākṛteśa G: soḍhaḥ
kleśo Ko2: mahākṛteśa G: mahān L: kṛtomayā |
G: khalu||

09

tatkāle'drṣṭadivyanām divyavācā śrutā mayā||
adrṣṭā prārthitā paścāt drṣṭatvaṃ bhava sāmpratam |

G: tatkāle dr° A2: tatkāle drṣṭadi° A1, Ko1, L,
Pa: tatkāle drṣṭadravyāṇi B: tatkāle adrṣṭadra-
vyānām J1: tatkāle draṣṭadravyāṇi Ko2: ta-
tkāle drṣṭe divyā, ni P: tatkāle drṣṭadravyāṇi
R: tatkāla drṣṭadravyāṇām U: tatkāle drṣṭidi-
vyā G: hivya° A1: divyācā A2, R: divyā J1,
Ko1, P, Pa: divyā vācā A2: add vācaḥ G: add
mayā R: add vāṇi mayā R: śruttā/ G, R: om
J1: mavā Ko1: adrṣṭa Pa: adrṣṭa U: adrṣṭvā
A1, L, R: adrṣṭaprā° Pa: pārthitā G: add devī
A2, Ko1: paścān G: draśyatva B: drṣṭatvaṃ
Ko2: drṣṭvā tvam R: drṣṭā tvam U: drṣṭā
U: cāmbhava Ko2: syāmpratam 9 R: māmpra-
tam//

vaṭayakṣaṇy uvāca

G, R: add śrī A1, J1, L, P: śrīvaṭayakṣarāja
 A2: śrīvaṭayakṣa B: śrīvaṭayakṣaṇī G: va
 Ko1: śrīvaṭayakṣarāja R: vaṭayakṣiṇy
 Pa: śrīvaṭayakṣarājauvāca| A2: add eka G: add
 nī A2: vāca Ko2: uvācā°|

10

sādhu sādhu mahāsiddha tvadbhaktiyā tu mahattayā||
 yat kārye kāṅkṣitaṃ bhadra tat sarvaṃ pradadāmy ahaṃ| |

A1, Ko2: om A1, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: mahāsā-
 dhu A2, G: mahāsiddhaḥ A1, J1: ttadbhaktiyā
 G: tava bhaktiyā Ko1, P: ttarudbhaktiyā L: nna-
 rud bhaktiyā A1, G, J1, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, Pa: om
 A2: nu A2: mahātmanah 63 B: mahātmana|
 G, Ko2: mahātmanah J1: mahattadā L: ma-
 ddattayā| Pa: mahaṃmanah R: mahātmanā
 U: mahātmanah|| G: om Pa: yatkārye A1,
 J1, P: kāryed A2, U: kāryāt B: kāryā G: om
 Ko2: kāyī R: kāya A1, J1: kāni tāṃ A2: āhvā-
 nitā mahyaṃ B: hvānitā G: tatāhvānitā
 Ko1: kūni, taṃ Ko2: haṃ L: kāṃkṣitā P: kāni-
 tāṃ Pa: kānitā R: hārīto U: kāna Ko2, U: add
 te A2: tavaḥ Ko1: bhbhadra Ko2: bhadreḥ
 A2: paścā, t B, J1, Pa, U: tatsarvaṃ A2: om
 P: sarbaṃ A2: bravīmy G: ahadāmy Pa: pra-
 dadāmyahaṃ | 83

śrīnāgārjunovāca

A2 J1, L, P: om śrī° A1: nāgārjuno vāca G: śrī-
 nāgārjuna uvāca Ko1: nāgārjunovāca
 Ko2: nāgārju, novā° Pa: nāgārjuna|uvāca|"
 R: nāgārjunuvāca B: °rjuna uvāca||

11

tuṣṭā tvam yadi mām devi kṣiṣṭā dvādaśavarṣayā||
 ātmasatyam dade mahyam tataḥ paścād dhuvāmy ahaṃ| |

A2 A1, J1, Ko1, P: tuṣṭā G: tuṣṭā L: tuṣṭaḥ
 Pa: tuṣṭastvam Ko2: yaṃdi Ko2: mā U: mo
 A1, R: kṣṣṭā G: kṣiṣṭo J1: kaṣṭā Ko1: kṣṣṇāṣṭā
 Ko2: kṣiṣṭā L: drṣṭā P: kṣṣṭāṣṭā Pa: klaṣṭā
 Ko2: dvādasava° G: dvādaśa vatsaram
 L: 'ṣṭādvādaśavarṣakah| A1, J1, Ko1,
 P: °rṣakaīḥ Pa: °rṣakam| Ko2: ātmajñātvaṃ
 R: ātmāsatyam U: ātmajñatvaṃ G: dades
 Ko2: vahe R: ca te U: dahe G: matdyaṃ
 Ko2: mahyamḥ R: satyam Ko2: taḥṭa A1,
 P: paścā Ko2: paścādbham Pa: paścāddadā-
 myahaṃ|| B: budvayāmy G, R: vrvāmy

12

satyaṃ satyaṃ punaḥ satyaṃ aho vācā tridhā kṛtā||
yat kiñcit prārthase siddha tat sarvaṃ pradadāmy ahaṃ||

śrīnāgārjuno'vāca

13

yadi tvaṃ devi tuṣṭāsi madbhaktyā bhaktivatsale|
durlabhaṃ triṣu lokeṣu rasabandhaṃ dadasva me |

14

yena kenāpy upāyena prakaromi mahādbhutam|
sādhanaṃ sūtakasyāpi mṛtyudāridranāśanam |

J1: dhruvāmy Ko2: om U: bhavāmy

A1: om Ko2: śa₁tyaṃ₂ Ko2: om Ko2: pūnaḥ
Ko1: satyāṃ Ko2: satyaṃ_haho B: aye₁ G: om
R: maho A2: vācas J1: śācā B: kṛdhā G: mi-
thyā J1: dvidhā Ko2: trīdhā G: kathamaho||
Ko1: yan Ko2: yatā R: om Pa: yatkiñcitprā-
rthaye A1: kiñchit B: kiñ...t J1: keṃ₁'₁ cit
Ko2: kecita A1: prārthaye B, L, P: prārthayese
G: prārthayate J1: prārthayet Ko1: pārthayese
R: prārthaya Ko2: prārthasesīdhiḥ R: add me
J1: siddhaḥ Ko2: ta A1, B, J1, Pa, U: tatsa-
rvaṃ Ko2: śarvaṃ P: sarbaṃ A1, A2, B, J1,
U: pramadāmy R: prarudābhy Pa: prada-
dā₁myahaṃ

A1, Ko2

B: tuṣṭāsi R: om B: add me Ko2: devī R: om
G: tuṣṭāsi J1: tuṣṭosi₁ Ko2: tuṣṭāsiḥ B: sarvva-
dā R: add me devi G: madbhātayā Ko2: ma-
bhaktyā R: sarvadā A2: bhaktava° Ko2: bha-
ktīvachaleḥ U: bhaktivachale|| A1, J1, Ko1, L,
P: °tsalaḥ G: °tsalo|| Pa: °tsalaṃ| B: rlabhaṃ
J1: dulebha G: bhiṣu Ko2: lokaṣu A1, Ko1,
L: rasabaṃdha G: rasabaṃdhanam J1: rasa-
vaṃdhi G: vadādhunā|| J1, L: varānena A1,
A2, Ko1, Ko2, P, Pa, U: varānane G, J1, L: om

J1: yetā Ko2: e₁na A2: kenāth Ko1: kenāṣ
Pa: kenāpyu₁pā° L: kenābhyupā°
P: kenāṣupā° Ko2: kenāpyüpāena A2: upāye-
na J1: u₁pāye B, J1, R, U: prakaroti Ko2: pra-
kaśati J1: add si P: add zha₁ A1, Ko1, Ko2,
Pa: mahadbhutam B: mahadabhuta| J1: ma-
hadbhulamtaṃ L: mahadadbhutam| P: ma-
dadbhutam A1: sādanaṃ Ko2: sāvanaṃ B: sā-
dhanamaṣū° Ko2: sutakasyāpiḥ A2: mṛtpra-
dā° Ko2: mṛtudāridranāśanam 14 G: °ridyāna-
śanam|| R: °ridryanāśanam

15

parvatā grhaprāsādāḥ saśailavanakānanāḥ|
kāñcanamayāḥ kariṣyāmi lokānāḥ hitakāmyayā |

G, Pa: parvata P: parbatā R: parvat U: parva-
tād Ko2: grahe prāsādā U: grahaprāsā₁ dāt A1,
J1, Ko1, P, Pa: °sādā B, G, R: °sāda J1: sasai-
la° A1, Ko1, P: sasailavanakānanā B: saśaula-
vanakānanā| Ko2: sailavanakānanā R: maśai-
lavanakānanān G: °nanam|| Pa: °nanā|
Pa: kāmcanam mayā A1, J1, Ko1, L, P: °mayā
A2, B, G, R, U: °mayam Ko2: °maya B, R: pra-
vakṣyāmi Ko2: kariṣyāmī... J1: lokānā U: lo-
hānām Ko2, L: om A1: hitakāmya... 50

16

bhojanam vastratāmbūlam svasakhābhyo dadāmy aham||
ātmakhyātam kariṣyāmi asmimś ca pṛthivītale |

Ko2, L: om A2, B: vastratāmbūlam G, J1,
R: vastratāmbūlam Ko2, L: om P: va-
stratāmbūlam A1, Pa: sakhāye A2, P: sa-
sakhāyaiḥ B: vā śaśādyaiḥ J1: samakhāye
Ko1, U: sasakhāyai Ko2: om R: samaśādyaiḥ
L: asti A1, A2, B,
J1, Ko1, P, Pa, R, U: pradāpayet Ko2:
asmin L: om A2: ānmakhātiḥ B, G: ātma-
khyātiḥ L: om R: ātmakhyābhi₁r yathā
tiṣṭhed Ko2: tu B: add yathā tiṣṭe B, L: om A1,
J1, Ko1, P, Pa: asti G: asmimś L: om U: asmitu
A1, B, Ko1, Pa: om A2: tu J1: sa P: pu U: 2tha
L: sup^o Ko1, Pa: sup^o A1: supṛthivītalke 51
G: pṛthivītale|| Ko2: pṛthivītale 15 U: 1pṛthivītale||

17

devy upāyam varārohe kathayasva prasādataḥ |

A2: tam B, G, U: tad R: ud Ko2: tayā₁yām
Pa: divyupāyam A2, B: upāya B: carārohe
Ko2: varāroheḥ R: kaṣayasva J1: prasātataḥ
Ko2: varānane 16

vaṭayakṣiny uvāca

G: add śrī A1: vaṭayakṣany A2: vaṭagrakṣaṇa
B: vaṭayakṣany G: vaṭayakṣinī J1: vaṭayakṣa
Ko2: vaṭayakṣanyū L: vaṭayakṣany uvāca
P: vaṭayakṣaty R: vaṭayakṣiny
Ko1: vaṭa₁yakṣatyuvāca Pa: vaṭayakṣaitiyuvā-
ca|| U: |vaṭayakṣanyuvāca||| A2, Ko2: vāca

18

yat kiñcit prārthayeh siddha tat sarvam pradadāmi te|

Ko2: add sādhuḥ mahāsiddha A2: ya Ko2: tvat

kuru kāryaṃ yathātathyāṃ tiṣṭhe'haṃ tvatsamīpataḥ |

J1: yatkiṃcit Pa: yatkiṃcitprārthaye
 Ko2: add bhaktyā tu mā₁tmanah
 Ko2: yatkiṃcītārthaṃ A1, G: prārthyate
 A2: prārthase B: prārthyase J1, Ko1, L,
 P: prārthaye R: pra₁klrse U: prārthate
 Ko2: add te B, R: bhadra J1: siddhaḥ Ko2: si-
 dhiḥ U: siddhi J1, Pa: tatsarvaṃ A2: sarva
 P: sarbaṃ U: pravādāmi J1: pradadāmyate
 R: aham G: kṛta Ko2: ku sa ru A2: kārya
 J1: kārgaṃ Ko1: kārthaṃ R: dravyaṃ Ko1,
 L, P: yathātavyaṃ Ko2, U: yathātithyaṃ A1,
 B, G: tiṣṭe haṃ A2, J1: tiṣṭehaṃ Ko1, P, R,
 U: tiṣṭhe haṃ R, U: tatsa° Ko2: tvaśamī₁pata
 P: tvastsamīpataḥ

19

sarvalakṣaṇasampūrṇo yaḥ sulakṣasya poṣakaḥ |
 tasya sparśāvalokena yuṣmatsiddhir bhaviṣyati |

P: sarbala° Ko1: sarvalaṃ₁kṣa° Ko1: ya
 Pa: yassu° G: yastu la° A2: yasva la°
 Ko2: yasulakṣastū J1, L, P: sūla° A1: tu la°
 B: tu lakṣasy R, U: tu lakṣas R, U: add tu
 B: upo° Ko2: poṣaka 18 R: poṣitaḥ R: mparśā°
 A1: sparśava° Pa: sparśavilo° Ko2: sarsavilo°
 A1, Ko1, P: yuṣmasiddhir Ko2: yūṣmasidhi
 R: yuṣmāsiddhir Pa: yuṣmatsidhirbha-
 viṣyati | 91 Ko2: bhavi₁ṣyatiḥ

20

mayā tasya śrutaṃ vākyaṃ prārthitaḥ śālivāhanaḥ |
 yuṣmatsāmarthyayogena sādhyāmi mahārasam |

Ko2: māyā R: sayā G: śrūtaṃ G: vācyaṃ A1,
 Ko1, Ko2: prārthita J1, L, P: prārthitaśā°
 R: sā₁li° Ko2: sālivāhana 19 R: yuṣmatmāma°
 U: yuṣmāt sāma° Ko2: yuṣmat sāmarthayo°
 Ko2: add na B: maha₁rasam||97

śrīśālivāhanovāca

A1: śrī śālivāhanvāca A2: śrīśālivāhana uvāca
 B: śrī śālivāhana uvāca G, R: śālivāhana uvāca
 J1: śrīśālivāhanobāca Ko1: śrīśālivāha-
 novācaḥ Ko2: sālivāhanovāca L: śrīśālivāha-
 novāca | P: śrīśālivāhanovāca Pa: śrīśālivāha-
 nauvāca | U: iti śālivāhana uvāca|||

21

suvarṇaratnabhāṃḍāraṃ kumārī mama sundarī |
 niveditaṃ mayātmānaṃ ādeśo deva diyatām |

A1: °tnanāmbhāraṃ Ko2: °tnabhaṃḍāraṃ
 R: °bhāṃḍa₁Lraṃ A1, J1, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, Pa,

22

sādhu sādhu mahāprājña mamādeśaprapālakaḥ|
sādhayāmi na sandeho yuṣmatsatyena sādhaḥ |

U: kumāro G: kumāreṇa ca A1: masu A2: ma-
dana B: mana Ko2: dime R, U: mada Ko2: su-
dari zo J1: nivedita Ko2: niveditaṃ
J1: māyā° G: mayātmāna Ko2: ādeso Ko2,
U: devi A1, Ko1, P: dāyatāṃ G, J1: diyatā
Ko2: diyatoma

23

punar anyama pravakṣyāmi māṇḍavyena yathā kṛtam|
rasoparasayogena siddhasūtaṃ susādhitaṃ |

A1, Ko2: om P: madhu Ko2: māhā°
L: mahāprāsa R: mahāprājñā R: samā°
J1: mamādeśaḥ pra° B, Pa: mamādēśa pra°
A1: jñamādeśaprapālaka Ko2: mamadesapra-
pālaka 21 G: °śa prapālaka|| A2: °laka Pa: sā-
dhiyāmi Ko2: ni A2: saṃdehaṃ
Ko2: saṃdehoḥ Ko2: uṣma° A2: yuḥsmatsa-
tvena Ko1: yuṣmatsanyena R: yuṣmansetyena
A2, J1, Ko1, L, P, U: sādhaḥ Pa: sādhaḥ
ḥ 94 R: mādhakam

24

viddhaṃ sulvāyasaṃ nāgaṃ yajñārthe kāñcanaṃ kṛtam|
tasya pārśve vaśiṣṭhena rasakarmāvadhāritam |

A1: puṇyar B: punaṃr P: puṇyanar
Pa: puṇnar G: anyat J1: ratnaṃ Ko2: pra-
vakṣāmī A1, J1, Ko1, L: māḍa°
B: māṇḍavyēna Ko2: māṇḍavyena J1: krama
Ko2: kramaṃ Ko2: add tyaṃ 22 J1: °ramayo-
gena Ko2: °rasamyogena A2, B, G, R, U: si-
ddhaṃ sūtaṃ J1: siddhisūtaṃ Ko2: si-
dhamsuḥ taṃ Ko2: sūsādhita

A1, Ko1: vidvaṃ B, R: viddha G: viḍaṃ
A2: śulvā° B: śulyāyasaṃ G: sulvāsasaṃ
Ko2: sūlvāyasa R: sulvāyanaṃ U: sulbāyasaṃ
J1: śulvāyasaṃnāgaṃ Pa: °saṃnāḥ gaṃ
A1: yajñārthēṃ A2: yajñārthṃ B: pajñārthe
G: prajñārthe Ko2, U: yajñārthaṃ R: yathā-
rthe Ko2: kañcanaṃ J1, Ko2, U: tasyā
Ko2: parasve L: pārśve°va° R: māravaḥ miṣṭhena
Ko2, U: viśi° A1: vaśiṣṭheṇa A2, Pa: vaśiṣṭhena
B: naśiṣṭhena G: vaśiṣṭhena Ko1, P: vaśiṣṭhena
Ko2: rasakāṃmava° R: rasakanmāva° B: rasa-
karmava° G: rasaka mavidhāritam|| Ko1: ra-
sakarma vidhāḥ ritam A2: °rmāḥ vadhāritam

77 P: °rmā vidhāritam

25

śāstram vaśiṣṭhamāṇḍavyam gurupārśve mayā śrutam |
tad ayam sampravakṣyāmi sādhanam ca yathāvidhiḥ | |

A1: śāsu J1: śāstu Ko2: sāstram
Pa: śāstramva° Ko2: vaśiṣṭam māṁ°
P: vaśiṣṭamāṁ° B: viśiṣṭamāṁ°
A2: vaśiṣṭamāṁ° A1: vaśiṣṭamāṇḍavyam
J1: vaśiṣṭhamāṇḍavyam
Ko1: vaśiṣṭhamāṇḍavyam
R: vaśiṣṭhasāṇḍavyam G: juru° B: guruṇā pā-
rśva Ko2: gurupārśve R: gurupārśvam B, R: ya-
thā R: om Ko1, L, P, Pa: tadayam A2, B, G,
J1, Ko2, U: aham R: udaham Ko2: sampra-
vakṣmi, A2: yathāvidhi 78 Ko1: yathāvidhiḥ
Ko2: yathāvidhi

26

sahāyāḥ śobhanā prājñā nirālasyaḥ ḍṛḍhavrataḥ |
kulīnāḥ pāpahinās ca sarvadharmā jitendriyāḥ | |

A1, B, G, Ko2: sahāyā P: om R: sahāyāḥ A2,
Pa: śobhanāḥ Ko2: sobhanā R, U: śobhanaḥ
R: prājño J1: nirālasyaā Ko2: nirālasā R: nirā-
lambha A2, J1, Ko2, Pa: ḍṛḍhavrataḥ Ko1,
P: ḍṛḍhavrajatā L: ḍṛḍhavrajah | U: ḍṛḍhavra-
tyah | A1: ḍṛḍhavraja tāktu lināpā° G: kulānā
J1, Ko1, P: kulīnā Ko2: kulīnā B: om
Ko2: pāpahinās A2: sadharmās ca, Ko2: sva-
dharmās ca P: sarvadharmā R: sadhanmās
ca, U: sarvadharmās ca G: dharmajñāsṽaji°
J1: jitaimdriyāḥ Ko1, Ko2: jitendriyā

27

koṣṭikā vakranālam ca gomayāṅgāram indhanam |
dhaminī lohapātrāṇi uśadhye kāñjikaṁ viḍam | |

Ko1: koṣṭikā P: koṣṭhikā L Pa: caṁkra° A1: va-
kranāmlam B, G: cāstunālam Ko2: vakravā-
lam U: cakravālam J1: add gomayām
J1: °gāni R: °gāras A1: gomayām gomaṁ, ryā-
gāni baṁdhanam Ko1, L, P, Pa: °gāni
baṁdhanam J1: vaṁdha, nam G: dhamanī
J1: dhabhinī Ko2: dhamani L: dhāminī
R: dhamanam U: dhāminīyam B: om
Ko2: add yam J1: lohayatrāṇi Ko2: loha-
pā, trāṁni A1, J1: uśadhyo A2: rtuśyedhyah
G: caṣakā Ko1, P: uśadhye Ko2, U: ośadhyā
Pa: aśadhyo R: auśadam A1: koṁjika G,
J1: kāṁjika R: kāṁcikaṁ A1: viddham

28

karppūrāṇi vicitrāṇi nānā mūṣā tathaiva ca |
sarvamelāpakam kṛtvā tat karma samācaret |

U: biḍam||

A2, Ko1, P, Pa: karpparāṇi J1: karppārāṇi
Ko2: yarvarāṇi R: kandarāṇi U: parvarāṇi
Ko2: vicitrāṇi B, G: nanā Ko2, U: mānā
R: nānas A1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: mūkhā B,
G: bhūṣās J1: mūkhām Ko2: muṣā R: yathā
Ko1: caḥ₁ P: sarbame° Ko2: sarvaṃ₁ me°
R: °param A1, Ko1, P: tata A2, B, G, Pa,
R: tataḥ Ko2, U: tato U: karmaṃ Pa: karma-
sa° A2, B, G: samārabhet R: masasārabhet

29

catuṣkatorāṇam mālākumbham vārisamanvitam |

J1: caḍaṣkaṃ to° A2, R: catuṣkaṃ to°
A1: catuḥkaṣkaṃ₁ taraṇam B, G: catuṣpada-
reṇam Ko2: catuṣkaṃtorāṇa B, G: mālā-
kaṃbham J1: mālāLkubham Ko1, R: mālām
kumbham Ko2: mālāmkaṃbham Pa: mālā |
kaṃṭam A2: vārisaLmaṃnvitam Ko2: vārisa-
manvīta 28₁

30

sitacandanaliptāṅgam sitavastrāvagumṭhitam ||
pañcaratnasamaṃ cūrṇam dipākṣatasamanvitam ||

Ko2: sinacaṃdanaliptaṅgam A1, J1,
Ko1: °ptāṅga L, U: om J1: sitavasuva-
gumṭhanam Ko2: °vaguḍanam A1,
Ko1: °gumṭvanam P, Pa, R: °gumṭhanam
A1: paṃcaṃratnam samaṃ R: paṃcaratnam
sumam Ko2: °tnasusam A2: °sa₁ māyuktaṃ
A2: om J1: tulyam Ko2: purṇa R: pū₁ ṇam B,
G: cūrṇadī° A1, J1, Ko1, P, Pa: dipākṣita°
A2: dipākṣasamaṃnvitam Ko2: dipākṣata-
manvīta 29₁

31

pīṭham catuṣkamadhyastham sthāpayitvā mahāmuniṃ |
candanāgurudhūpaiś ca naivedyair vividhais tathā |

A1, J1, Ko1, L, P: paṭhan Ko2: piṭham
Ko2: catuṣkaṃ U: catuṣkasamyuktaṃ
J1: °dhyastha Pa: °dhyattham | Ko2: add
samyuktaṃ A1, J1, Ko2: mahāmuni A2,
Pa: mahāmuniḥ R: mahāsane A2,
J1: caṃdanā gu° U: caṃdanā garu° A1, B,
G: caṃdanā gurūdhūpaiś Ko2: caṃdanāgaru-
dhūpaiś Pa: °dhūpaiś A1: naivedhvai A2: ne-

32

mahāprājñā prakarttavā ciraṃ bhojaṃ ca kārayet|
kumārikās tathā pūjyā ājñāṃ tu prārthayen naraḥ|

vedyair J1, P: naivedyai Ko1: naivedye L: nai-
vedhair Pa, R: naivadyair B, G: vidhais J1: vi-
vādhes Ko2: vividhīs R: viLrvividhais

33

yūṣmadājñāprasādena sādhyāmi mahārasam|
ādau tāvad rasam grāhyaṃ viśuddham nirmalam dṛḍham|

A2, Ko2, R, U: mahāpūjā Pa: mahāprajñā A1,
Ko1, L, P, Pa: pravartavyā J1: pracarttavā
Ko2: vira Pa: mavīraṃ R: cyāvīraṃ U: vīra
A2: vīrabhojyaṃ B, G: mahābhojaṃ L: bhijaṃ
R: bhojya Ko2, U: tu Ko2: puja U: pūjā A1,
J1, Ko1, Ko2, L: ājñā Ko2, U: tat Ko2: prā-
rthae Ko2: nara 31 1

Ko2: yūṣmadā° A1: °pra1sadena U: add
sādena A1: ākṣai A1: tābadva Ko2, U: hi
R: bhāvad Pa: tāvadasaṃ U: rasa Ko2: rasa
saṃgrāhyaṃ U: saṃgrāhyaṃ A1: visuddha
J1: viśuddha Ko1, P: visuddham Ko2: viśū-
dham J1: nirmala B, G: nirmaladrḍham

34

dravye rasāyane योग्यां तताः कर्मा समारभेत|
सुमृष्टां पतितं सूतां सर्वदोषोर्जितां तताः|

A1, J1, Pa: dravyaṃ Ko2: dra1vya R: duṣṭa
Ko1, L, P, U: rasāyena Ko2: rasāyane R: remā-
yane| B, G: add na B, G: ta Ko1: tat Ko2,
U: tato U: karmaṃ A2, Ko1, L, P, R, U: samā-
rambhet B, G: suhrṣṭaṃ Ko2: sudṛḍham
R: sujṛṣṭaṃ U: sughrṣṭaṃ L, R: pānitaṃ
Ko2: sutaṃ R: pūtaṃ A1: sarvadoṣāptitaṃ
Ko1: sarvadoṣādbhitaṃ Ko2: sarvado-
soschitaṃ Pa: sarvadojitaṃ B, G: °ṣo śita
J1: °ṣotitaṃ L: °ṣodbhiḥ taṃ P: °ṣodbhitaṃ1
R: °ṣojkitaṃ U: °ṣosthitaṃ Ko2: tata 33

35

rasakasatvasaṃyogā jīrṇam aṣṭaguṇe naraḥ|
kṛṣṇābhraṃ sūtaṃ lolayitvā tu jārayet|

B: rasakaḥ sa° R: rasakasam sa° J1: rasakaḥ
sarvasaṃyogo Ko2: rasaka1tvasaṃyogā U: ra-
sakaḥ śulbasaṃyogā A1: °tva1 saṃyogā
G: °tva saṃyogāt Ko1, L, P, Pa: °gā
Ko2: jīrṇam R: jīrṇe Pa: jīrṇamaṣṭaguṇo
Ko2: aṣṭagūṇe R: duṣṭa1guṇe U: aṣṭaguṇai B,
G: aṣṭaguṇottaraḥ| J1: nna1raḥ Ko2: nara
Ko2: kṛṣṇā° R: kṛṣṇābhra° Pa: kṛṣṇācaka° B,

36

samena gandhakaṃ dadyāt agnisomaṃ na nirdahet|
tīkṣṇaṃ śulvaṃ sunāgaṃ ca samāvarttaṃ ca kārayet|

G: °ka samaṃ U: kṛṣṇābhraṅkaṃ sasamsūtaṃ
A1: sūta L: sulo° Ko1, P: sūlo° R: lāla° A1: lo-
layitkā A1: nu

37

uṣmayantrasya madhyasthaṃ jāritavyaṃ prayatnataḥ|
punar anyam prakartavyaṃ yathā carati kāñcanaṃ|

Ko2, U: om J1: agniśoṃmyaṃ A2, Pa, R: agni-
somena B: amagni śoṣena G: agniśomena
J1: niddahet R: nindahet| R: tīkṣṇāṃ
J1: tīkṣṇasulvaṃ A1, Pa: sulvaṃ Ko1, L,
P: sutvaṃ J1: sunāga R: sanāgaṃ P: add sa-
māvarttaṃ ca kā J1: samāvartta R: mamāva-
ntaṃ A1: add kā samā 69 varttaṃ ca
A1: kāra° J1: kāmsayāt

R: kūṣma° J1: ūṣma° B, G, U: uṣmayam°
A1, A2: kuṣmayam° Ko2: yuṣmayam| trasa
Ko2: maṃvyasthaṃ Ko2: prayatnata G: anyat
J1: ratnaṃ Ko2: anyam A1: prakatrāvyam
Ko1, P: prakartāvyam Ko2: caratī L: varati
R: carita Ko2: kāñcana 35

38

gokarṇā ca samākhyātā dvitīyā kṛṣṇamañjarī|
yathālābhe grhātavyā viśeṣo nopalabhyate|

A1, A2, G, J1, Pa: gokarṇī B: gokarṇī Ko2: go-
karṇī R: gokarṇe J1: samākhyāto
Ko1: °jarīḥ Ko2: °jari B, G: yathālābham
Ko2: yathālābho Pa: yathā lābhe A1,
Ko1: grhātavyā Ko2: prakartavyā A1, J1, Ko1,
L, P: viśeṣo pa B, G: viśeṣā cetra Ko2: viśeṣā
U: viśeṣā A1, J1, Ko1, L, P: na labhyate B,
G: labhyate Pa: nopalabhyamta| R: naiva la-
bhyate

39

yatra deśe samutpannā bhūtale vātha parvate|
samaye tatra nirdiṣṭā yeneyaṃ saphalā bhavet|

A2: yatre Ko2: yam| tra G: yatradeśe
U: yamtradeśe A2: dśe Ko2: dese P: kṣeśe
R: deśo A1, B: samupannā Ko2: samutyanā
G: samupannābhū° L: vādya U: cātha A2: pa-
rvateḥ 91 L: parvate| P: parbate R: vantate
J1: om R: tanmaye A2: tatra A2: yenedam
J1: add samaye A2, U: saphalm B, G, Ko2: sa-
phalam

40

tasmāt sarvaprayatnena dṛśyamantreṇa saṅgrhet|

Ko2: tasmā₁ Pa: tasmātsarvaṃ pra° P: sarba-
pra° A2, J1: sarvaṃ pra° B: daśya° R: daśa-
maṃ° Ko2: dṛśyamaṃ° J1: dṛśyamamṭraṇa
Ko1, L, P: dṛśyamamṭraṇa A2, G: saṃgrahet
B, Ko2, U: saṃgrahe Pa: saṃgrmhat 14

mantraḥ

A1, G, J1, R Ko2: matra L, P: maṃtraṃ Pa,
U: maṃtra||

41

om namas te mṛtasambhūte balavīryī vivardhane
balaṃ āyus ca me dehi pāpān me jahi dūrataḥ||

B: aṃ A1, A2, J1, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, Pa, U: om
G, R: namaste B: amṛtasambhavate R: mṛta-
masbhūte B: balavīryaṃ R: valavīry B, R: viva-
rdhani G: balaṃbīrya R: sa₁makārya G: meho
R: kṛte G: hi R: devi R: punaḥ R: svargaṃ
R: gamiṣyati G: durataḥ|| R: om

42

yenedaṃ khanate brahma yenedaṃ khanate hariḥ
tenāhaṃ khanayīṣyāmi pañcasankhyena pāṇinā

A2, Ko2, U: om B: yena om R: yena tvām
J1: om G: ravanate Ko2: śanate U: khanayete
A1, B, Ko2, Pa, U: brahmā A2, P, R: vrahmā
G: bhramā B: yena om Ko2: enedaṃ R: yena
tvām A2: yenedaṃ₁kha° Ko2, U: śanate
A2: add raviḥ|| A1, Ko1, Ko2, Pa: hari B,
R: bhrguḥ B: add yena imdro tha varuṇo
R: add yena śakro śaL varuṇas B: tenaitam
G: yenāhaṃ R: tenaivam B: add upacakrame|
etat te R: add upacakrame pa tena U: śana°
B: dhana° A1: khanayāṣyāmi Ko2: śana-
yīṣyā₁Lmi R: khanayipyāmi Ko1: °ṣyā₁mī A1,
Ko2, Pa: pañcasakhyena A2: pañcaśākhena
B: brahmapūtena G: pāñcasāṃkhena R: vra-
sta sūtena U: pañcasavyena Ko2: pāṃṇinām
38

mantraḥ |

A1, B, Ko1, Pa A2, P: add om A2: mā G: śrīḥ
J1: atha Ko2, U: maṃtra L, P: mātṛā
R: maṃtraṃ

43

utpatti patitoṣṭake tiṣṭha tiṣṭha sureśvarī|
sādhayitvā tu me kāryaṃ paścāt sarge gamiṣyasi|

A1: add uṃmātṛā B: add ma G, U: add mā A2,
U: utpata B: utpate G: utpatat Ko2: mānatya-

ta Pa: tiumām̐khau₁ ...ti R: ...mātaṣyate
 A2: niyata B: māpatate G: nipatate J1: pati-
 toṣṭhake Ko2: nipatīte Pa: pāta..... R: māpa-
 tane U: nipatite B: add māti tejño bhṛśā ma
 vetā A2, J1, P, Pa, U: tiṣṭa B: a₁traiva R: māti-
 teno₁ A2, J1, P, Pa, U: tiṣṭa Ko2, R: om
 G: tiṣṭhasu° B: add kalyāṇi mama B: kāryakarī
 Ko2: suresvari L: surekharī R: om B: bhava
 Ko2: sādha_itvā R: nyathā R: add bhavet
 atraiva B: om R: tiṣṭa kalyāṇi B, R: mama B,
 G: kārya R: kāryakṛtī B: kṛte Ko2: paścā R: om
 Pa: paścātsarge B: add siddhi A2, P: svarge
 B: svargalokaṃ G: svarga Ko2, U: sarve R: om
 G: gamiṣyati|| Ko2: bhaviṣyati 39 R: bhava
 U: bhaviṣyasi||

44

anenaiva tu manreṇa kuryāt saptābhimantritam|
 uttāpya arkasaṃyogāt chāyām̐ śuṣkām̐ tu kārayet |

G: pāne naiva R: rta Ko1, L: kurpyāt
 Ko2: kuryāta R: kutān J1, P: kuryātsaptā°
 Pa: kuryātsaptābhimantritam| B: saptabhi°
 Ko2: śaptābhimantritam R: maptābhi-
 mantritāt A2, U: utpādyā arkka°
 Pa: utpā₁pra karmasaṃ° P: utpādyakarma-
 saṃ° A1, J1, Ko1, L: utpādyā karmasaṃ°
 G: utpādyā ravisam̐yogācca Ko2: utpādyā₁
 arkasaṃyogā R: utya₁yahr̥tkasaṃyogāśchāyā
 A1, J1: bāyā A2, Ko2, L, P, U: chāyā B: chāyo
 G: yā Pa: chāya Ko1: chāyāsuṣkām̐ A1, P,
 Pa: suṣkām̐ B: suṣkān G: suṣkā J1: suṣkaṃ
 Ko2: suṣka R: suṣkaṃstu G, Ko2, U: ca

45

dadhnā sā madhukāṣṭhena yāvad bhasma na gacchati|
 sakalā sā bhaved devī mṛtyudāridranāśinī |

G: dugdhā J1: dagdhā Ko2: om R: ca
 U: sāma° A2, B, G, Ko1, P, Pa, R: madhu-
 kāṣṭhena G: yāradyu A2, P, R: yāvadbhasma
 Pa: yāvadbhasmaṃ B, U: bhasmaṃ J1: bha-
 śmaṃ L: rasma R: ca R: gaśchati G: saphalā
 U: sam̐kalā U: bhava P: bhaveddevī G: devi
 G: °ridryanāśinī|| R: °ridrānāśinī B, U: °nāśa-
 nī A2: °śinīḥ 96

46

uṣmayantrasya madhyastham oṣadhī rasakāñcanam|
 athavā viḍayogena jārayet tu vicakṣaṇaḥ |

R: kūṣmāyan° A1, G, J1, P, Pa: uṣmayam°

Ko2, U: uṣmayamtreṇa A2: °traspa
 G: maṁdhyasthaṁ J1: madhyastha Ko2: ma-
 dhāyasthaṁ R: madhyasthamoṣadhi A1, J1,
 Ko1: uṣadhī A2: oṣe₁dhī G: āuṣadhī
 Ko2: oṣadhi P: uṣadhīra° Pa: aṣadhīra°
 B: oṣadhīra° Ko2: rasa kaṁcanaṁ A2: atha vā
 Ko2: 'l thavā P: athavāvīḍa° U: bīḍa° J1, Ko1,
 L: vīḍa° Pa: baḍa° A1: bīḍa° B: add na J1,
 P: jārayitvā Ko2: āvad A1, Ko1: jārayitu
 R: jāyae₁te Pa: jārayattadvicakṣaṇaḥ | 19 B,
 J1: om Ko2: dinacatuṣṭayaṁ 41Skip to srisai-
 la48a G: vicakṣāṇāḥ|

47

ūrdhve vahnir adhaś cāpa madhye tu rasasaṁsthitāḥ|
 kāñcanaṁ jāyate sūta agniṁ dattvā muhur muhuḥ |

A1 G: ūrdhva J1, Ko2: urdhvaṁ Ko1, P,
 U: urdhve Pa: urdho R: urdha B: vahnirm
 G: vahnir Ko2: bahi U: vahvim R: vahnima-
 dho P: vahnirardhaścāpa Pa: vahniradhaścā-
 paṁ | B: adhaḥ Ko1, L: ardhaś Ko2: madhaś
 B: āpa G: cāpo R: āpaḥ U: cāpaḥ| A2: cāpoma-
 dhye Ko2: cāpamadhe G: ca Ko1: tru Ko1, L,
 P: ravisam° J1, Pa: ravisamsthitam Ko2: rasa-
 nvīta U: rasam anvitaḥ || G: °sthitih|| G,
 Pa: kācanaṁ Ko2: kāṁcane₁ A2: cārayet B,
 G, Pa, U: jārayet Ko2: jāra_eta R: jārayetsūte
 agniṁ A2, G, U: sūte agniṁ B, J1, Pa: sūtam
 agniṁ Ko1, P: sūta agni Ko2: sūte Ko2: add
 ajñī Ko2: om A2, B, G, Pa, R: muhurmuḥuḥ
 Ko1, P: muhurmuḥu Ko2: mṛḥumṛhū 42

48

anena kramayogena yāvad dinacatuṣṭayaṁ|
 sphoṭayeḥ jalamadhyasthaṁ prakṣālya nirmalaṁ kuru |

Ko2: om J1: karmayo° Ko1: yāva A2, B, P, Pa,
 R: yāvaddina° A2: sphoṭāyajaḥ B: sphoṭaye
 U: sphoṭye Pa: sphphoṭayejjala°
 R: smosphoṭayojjala° P: sphoṭayejjalama-
 dhyamsthaṁ U: kajjala° A2, R, U: prakṣālyaṁ
 B: prakṣālyaṁ B: punaḥ| | 22 R: tataḥ

49

unmattamunipatrāṇi rajanī kācamācīkā|
 etāni samabhāgāni āranālena peṣayet |

B R: tatpatramani° G: °niratrāṇi Ko2: om A2,
 P: rajanīkā° J1: kācimā° G: kācamātrīkā||
 R: mtastara° J1: āranā A1, P: lepe°
 A2: pīṣayet 100 J1: lepayet

50

anena kramayogena yāvat saptadināvadhiḥ|
paścād dvandvaḥ prakartavyo divyauśadhīrasena ca |

B Ko2: karmayo° R: yāvatsaptadināvadhim
A2, G: °vadhi Ko2: °vadhi Ko1: paścām P: pa-
ścādvaṃdva Pa: pa₁ścādbaṃdha R: pa₁ścā-
dvandha A1, J1: vaṃdva A2: vaṃdhaḥ
G: vaṃdham Ko1: dvaṃdva Ko2: vaṃdha
L: dvaṃdvaṃ U: baṃdha Ko1: prakartavyau
R: prakartavyaṃ A1: divyauśa° Pa: di-
vyośadhī° A2, G, U: divyauśadhībalena
Ko2: divyośadhībalena R: divyauśadhīvalena
Ko2, U: tu

51

kukkuṭāṇḍanibhaṃ sūtaṃ cūrṇayitvā vicakṣaṇaḥ|
brahmapuṣpasya niryāsaṃ puṭaṃ catvāri dāpayet|
mañjiṣṭhākṛtaniryāsaḥ tenaivaṃ tādr̥saṃ kuru |

A2: kuku₁tām° U: kurkuṭām° Pa: kurkaṭām°
A1, Ko1, P: kukaṭām° G: kakkuṭām manibha
J1: kurkuṭāṃḍaṃnibhaṃ Ko2: ku-
rkaṭāṃḍanibhaṃ R: kukkuṭāṇḍanibhaḥ B: °ni-
bhaḥ R: mūtaṃ Ko1: cūrṇa₁yitvā
Ko2: cūrṇa_itvā Ko2: vicakṣaṇa Ko2: vra-
hma° A2: vrahmapuṣpasya Pa: brahma-
puṣpasya A2: niryāsaḥ R: niryā₁me
Ko2: puṭa Pa: puṭaṃ A2: pu₁ṭaca° G: om
B: datvāri A2, U: māñjiṣṭhākṛtaniryāsaṃ
Ko1: māñjiṣṭhākṛtaniryāsa
Ko2: māñjiṣṭhākṛtaniryāsaṃ P: māñjiṣṭhākṛta-
niryāsaṃ Pa: māñ jī ṣṭhākṛta niryāsaṃ | A1,
J1: °ryāsaṃ B, R: om A2, G: tenaiva Ko1: tai-
naivaṃ Ko2: tatraiva P: tai₁nevaṃ U: tatrai-
ve₁ Ko2: tādr̥saṃ U: kuruḥ||

52

sephālikṛtaniryāsaṃ puṭaṃ catvāri dāpayet|
kāsmīrasya rasenaiva tenaiva tādr̥saṃ kuru||

U: sephālī|kr° G: śephālikotpani° B: om
R: om A1, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: om A2: puṭa
B: om Ko2: pūṭaṃ B: om B: om G: drāpayet||
A2: kāsmīrasya R: kāsmīrika Ko2: kāsmī-
rasara° B: kāsmīrara°
Ko2: pūṭaṃm ekaṃ U: tenaivaṃ Ko2: om
Ko2: tu Ko2: add dāpayet

53

mātuliṅgarasenaiva puṭaṃ ekaṃ ca dāpayet|
tataḥ siddhaṃ vijāniyāt vedhaṃ śulvasya dāpayet |

R: mātulaṅga° A2: mātuliṅga° Ko2: mātu-
liṅgaṃra° Ko1, L, P: mātuliṅgaṃ ra°
Pa: °rasenaiva | A1, Ko1, L: pum J1: punam
Ko2: om P: pumekaṃ Pa: puṭameka A1: kaṃ

54

evaṃ jñātvā prayatnena kuru karma vicakṣaṇaḥ |
varṇasaṅkhyāpramāṇena nāgaṃ bhavati kāñcanaṃ |

Ko2: tenaiva A2, G, U: tu R: pradā°
Ko2: tāḍṛsaṃ kuru 46 B, Ko2, U: tato
R: tataLsmiddhiṃ A1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: śudhaṃ
J1: śudhi Ko2: śidhaṃ Ko2: vijānīyā R: °yān
B: veṣaṃ Ko1: vedvaṃ Ko2: dhedhaṃ
L: vednaṃ R: vedaṃ A1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: sulva-
sya Ko2: śulvāsa U: śulbasya Ko2: dāpa_et

55

athātaḥ saṃpravakṣyāmi karttārīrasabandhanam |
uparatnāni saṅgrhya bhūmiśailalatodbhavam |

J1: karpa B: vicakṣaḥ | 27 Ko2: vīcakṣaṇa 47
A1: varṇaṃsaṃ R: varṇamāpyāpra°
Ko2: vaṇasaṃśyāpramāṇena Pa: °khyā-
pramāṇena | A1: kocanaṃ 85 Pa: kācanaṃ |
A2: add ||ch| |

56

rasakādiṣu saṃyuktaṃ karttārīrasabandhanam ||
etāni samabhāgāni kapimūtreṇa bhāvayet |
etasya kusumenaiva capalaṃ ca puṭeḍ budhaḥ |

A1, Pa: athātaḥ Ko2: athāta G: om saṃ°
R: maṃ pra° Ko2: syaṃpravakṣāmi A2,
B: karttārī° R: karpūra ra° L: karttārara° G,
J1, Ko1: kartarira° A1, P: karttari ra° Ko2: ki-
rtirasyabaṃ Pa: kattari rasabadhanaṃ | 27
R: tamara° Ko2, U: om A1, Ko1, L, P,
Pa: bhūmaśai° A2: bhūmi śai la° B: bhūmiśi-
lalatodbhava | 28 J1: bhūmaśelakṛtau dbhu-
va R: bhūmiśūlatateto, dbhavam G: °todbhā-
vaṃ

57

hemadvādaśabhāgās ca ṣaḍbhāgās capalasya ca |
catuṣṣaṣṭhi rasendrasya ekikṛtya vimardayet |

A1, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: rasādiṣu Ko2, U: om
J1: saṃyukta J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: karttari ra°
A2, B, R: karttari ra° R: catāni Ko2: °gāni ...
Ko2, U: om A1: ___sya A2: tat tasya B: saṃta-
sya J1: brahmasya P: ___khyā Pa: _satasya
R: matamyasya ku° Ko1, L: khyaku° G: om
A2: kusame° A1: kusumainaiva Ko2: kusūme-
na ca J1, Ko1, L, Pa: puṭe Ko2: puṭe A1,
P: puṭeduḥ B: puṭeḍbudhaḥ | R: punavudhaḥ
J1: daduḥ Ko1, L: duḥ Ko2: būdhaḥ Pa: ta 29

G: imedvādasabhāyās Ko2: °da, sabhāgās B,
R: om J1: ṣaḍabhāgās Ko2: ṣaḍabhāgā Pa,
U: ṣaḍbhāgā G: ṣaḍbhāgāśrupa° Ko2: capalās

58

gostanākāramūṣāyāṃ andhayitvā puṭed budhaḥ |

U: om A2, J1, Ko1, Pa: catuṣṣaṣṭi G,
L: catuṣṣaṣṭi Ko2: catuṣṣaṣṭi P, U: catuṣṣaṣṭira°
A2, Ko1, L: rasemḍrsya Ko2: rasam ḍrsya
Ko2: ekaiḥkṛtvā U: ekai kṛtvā J1: mardayet
Ko2: vimardat 49

59

apare'hani samprāpte dhṃāpayitvā tu sphoṭayet|
śuddhasphaṭikasāṅkāśaṃ subaddhaṃ ḍrśyate rasaḥ|
paścād prakāṭamūṣāyāṃ samāvarttaṃ ca kārayet|
jīrṇe jīrṇe ca dātavyaṃ ajīrṇe na ca dāpayet |

A2: gostā, nā° Pa: gostanakāramūkhāyāṃ |
G: °ra bhūṣāthā J1: °ramukhāyā A1, Ko1, L,
P: °mūkhāyāṃ Ko2: °mūṣāyāṃ B, R: om
Ko2: adha° A2: samāvartta G: adha pitvā
J1: aṃdhatvā P: °tvāLpuṭedbudha A2: add tu
A1: puṭe A2: kārayet Ko2: pūṭe J1: puṭadbudhaḥ
A2: om Ko1: budha Ko2: būdha G: add
tat tasya kusumais caiva capalaṃ ca puṭed
budhaḥ

Ko2: ajñire° U: agnire° B, G: apare hani A1,
J1, Ko1, L, P: samprāpto A1, A2, B, G, J1,
Ko1, L, P, Pa, R: dhāmayitvā Ko2: dhamāpa-
yātvā Ko2: sphoṭa et 50 B: om śuddha°
A1: dvudhasphaṭikasamkhyāsaṃ J1: budhaḥ
sphuṭikakasaravyāsaṃ Ko1, L, P: dvudvu-
sphuṭikasamkhyāsaṃ Ko2: dvaspha, Lṭika-
saṃkāsaṃ Pa: śudhasphuṭika, saṃkāsaṃ |
A2, R: °kāśaḥ G: om A2: saṃ, śuddhaḥ B: sa-
śuddhaṃ J1: suvaddha Ko1, P: suvaddhaṃ
Ko2: subaṃdha R: suśuddho U: subaṃdhaṃ
A1: daśyāṃte J1: daśāṃte Ko2, U: rasaṃ
A1: paścā B, J1, Ko2, Pa, U: paścāt R: paścā-
tpraka° P: paścātpragaṭamūkhāyāṃ A2: om
A1: svagaṭamū, khāyāṃ B: prakāṭapreṣāyā
Ko1, L, Pa: praṅgaṭamūkhāyāṃ
Ko2: makaṭamuṣāyāṃ J1: °mūkhāyā A1: sa-
māvavurturtru B: samāvataṃ L: samāvarbuḥ
Ko2: °rttaṃtu J1, P: samāvarttu
Ko1: samā, varbu A1, Ko2, L: om B, R, U: tu
J1: jīrṇai R: jīrṇa A1: rava P: jīrṇeva J1,
Ko1: va Ko2: om L: vadārtavyaṃ Ko2: vādā-
vyaṃ R: dātavyamaḥjīrṇe A2, G: ajīrṇenaiva L,
P: nava B, Ko2, R, U: naiva Ko1: va L, P: om

60

caturviṣaṅgaṇaṃ hemaṃ sūtaṃ grasate yadā |
samāṃsabhakṣaṇaṃ kuryāt punar anye tu sūtake |

A1: caturviṣaṅgaṇaṃ B, R: caturviśaṅgaṇaṃ U: caturviṣaṅgaṇaṃ J1: °śadgaṇa A1, A2, Ko1, L: hema J1: hetuma P: hemaṃ A2: sūtaṃ Ko2: sūtaṃkaṃ A2, B: grasa Ko2: grāsate R: gamate A1, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: sadā B: dā ||32 B: sumāṃ A2, G: svamāṃ R: samāṃśabhaṃ Ko2: saṃmāṃsatmakṣaṇaṃ L: Lsamāṃsamakṣaṇaṃ U: samāṃśabhakṣaṇaṃ Ko2: punaranyena P: punaṃ ranye R: ūdhvaṃ Ko2: om U: na G: sūtake || Ko2: sūtake R: mṃsūtake

61

āruṣkaram utpalī sūrye nakṣatraṃ bhuvanodbhavam |
śītāgnisaṃsthītā hy ete pañcamī suvidārītā |

B, G, R: āruṣkam J1: arukaram Ko2: aruṣkar U: āruṣkar B: utpalo G: atpalī Ko2, U: utpale R: alpālī R: add rthāca A2, B, G, R: sūrya Ko2, U: nakṣatra R: nakṣatranā A1, Ko1, L, P: add tu J1: bhuvanādbhavam U: sītā A1, Ko1, P, Pa: śatā J1: saptaviṣasthītā Ko2: śīṃtagnisaṃsthītā L: śītāgnisaṃsthītā A1, J1: dy Pa: tu vi J1: vavi A2: bhūvidārīṇī 12 B: bhamidārīṇī | G: bhūvidārīṇī || Ko2: bhūvidārīṇī R: bhūmicārīṇī U: bhūvidārīṇī ||

62

ekaikasya tu madhyasthaṃ sthāpitavyaṃ dinatrayam |

Pa B: ekaika G: ekaikasyaiva B: om B: susthaṃ G: madyasthaṃ Ko2: maṃdhyesthaṃ R: saṃsthaṃ R: add tu A2: sthapi Ko2: sthāpitavyaṃ G: dine ...

63

dhūmākulena yantraṇa sthāpitavyaṃ dinatrayam |
eke deyaṃHypermetrical. yantrayogena pātivyam prayatnataḥ |

Ko1, L, P: °leta J1: patreṇa Ko2: yaṃtreṇa... L: yaṃtraīṣa R: yatnena... A1: sthāpitavyaṃ Ko1, P: sthāpatavyaṃ B, G, Ko2, R, U: om A2: om J1: eka Ko1, L: eve P: eveveyaṃ A1, Ko1, L: beyaṃ A2: dhūmākulena J1: bayam J1: yatra A2: yaṃtreṇa Ko1: °geta Ko2: pātivyam

63a

viśuddhaṃ taṃ vijānīyāt vakrasvedena svedayet |
rāśīvedavapuś caiva caitre sūryālayeṣu ca |

A1: viśurdhṛṃ Ko2: biśuddhaṃ R, U: viśuddhaṃ L: te G: °yā A2, G, J1, Pa: cakra °

64

melayec chaśiyogena vedāgniparvalocanaḥ|
etat sarvaṃ rasenaiva peṣayitvā rasasya ca |

Ko2: sakrat sve° U: sakṛtsvedana Ko2: svada-
yat 55 A2: śa rā śi° A1, J1: rāśivedevaputrais
B: rāśividavasus° G: rāśivahuvapus° R: rāśirvi-
dhircamuś Ko1, P: °vaputres° L, Pa: °vaputrais
A1, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: ca G: caitye Ko2: caitra
R: devayūnpāla° B, U: om Ko2: sūryala° A1,
Pa: sūyālakeṣu A2: sū ryālepeṣu J1: sūyālake-
pu Ko1, P: mūlvālakeṣu L: sūlvālakeṣu

65

ardhorddhvena pradātavyaṃ agnistho mriyate rasaḥ|
kukkuṭāṇḍanibhaṃ sūtaṃ cūrṇayitvā vicakṣaṇaḥ |

Ko2: melayed vaśi° G: melayec cuśi° R: mela-
yet middhayo° Pa: melayet ṭhasiyo° P: mala-
ye chamiyo° L: malayen namiyo° Ko1: mala-
yec chamiyo° J1: malaye chasiyo° B: mela, ye
śyamiyo° A1: malayechasi yo° U: om
B: vedāṃgni° R: vedāṃghnipa° G: vedāṃpri
pa° A2: vedāṃ hi pa° Ko2: vedāṃ hi parvalo-
canaḥ 56 P: °parbalocanaḥ J1: °cane J1, P,
Pa: etatsarvaṃ Ko2: savaṃ R: sarva
G: savaṃrisūnava G: poṣa° R: meṣa° A2,
B: piṣa° Ko2: rajasya

66

pūrvam eva vidhānena pakvaṃ vai ṣoḍaśaiḥ puṭaiḥ|
siddhaṃ taṃ vijānīyāt vedhī pañcaśateṣu ca |

A1, B, Ko1, P, Pa: adhorddhena A2, U: adho-
rddhe na G: adhor dvana J1, L: ardorddhena
Ko2: adhordhvaṃ R: adhotvena Ko2: tanu
dā° B: ca dā° A2, G, U: tu dā° J1: pradāta-
vyāṃ R: pradātavyamagni mthāsthāpayate
G: āgnispho J1: agnistho A1: _stati G,
U: mriyate Ko1, Pa: mriyate Ko2: mriyate
P: mrite J1: stīterasah G: kakku° U: ku-
rkuṭāṃ° Ko1, P: kukaṭāṃ° A2: kukuṭāṃ° A1,
Pa: kurkaṭāṃ° J1: kurkuṭāṃ manibhaṃ
Ko2: kurkuṭāḍa, nitaṃ B: kukuḍasūtaṃ
Ko2: sutam G: cūrṇānitvā A1: om J1: vi-
cakṣaṇa

Ko1, L, P: sarvam A2: pūrveṇaiva A1: om
Ko2: avi R: aiva Ko2: vadhā° G: pakvaṃ
Ko1: pakam P: pakamṣo Pa: kakvaṃ A2: pra-
deyaiḥ Ko1: add ṣo J1: ca G: ṣoḍaśai
G: puṭaḥ|| Ko2: sidha R: add uca J1: ta R: va

B, G, Ko2, U: ca R: vijānī 1yād J1, Ko1, L,
P: vidhāyate Ko2: vedhā Pa: vedham
A2: paumcāśa° Ko2: pacaśūteṣu Pa: yaṃvā vi-
dyeṣu R: °teṣva Ko1: v L: vā | P: va

67

dviguṇe yadi kartavyaṃ pūrvasaṃskāram uttamam |
triguṇaṃ ca bhaved bandhaḥ kramakrameṇa yojitam |

G: dviguṇaṃ Ko2: dhigūṇe A1: om J1: kartta-
vya Ko2: kratavyaṃ R: kaṃtravyaṃ R: pū-
rvaṃ saṃ° G: pūrvasaṃskāram Ko2: pūrv-
saṃsakāram B: pūrvvasa R: uttamam U: utta-
mamam || 1 Ko2: triguṇaṃ J1: trimuṇena
Ko1, L, P, Pa: triguṇena J1, Ko1: bhava
Ko2: bhavetr B: vadvaḥ G: baṃdham
J1: dvaṃdva Ko1, L: dvaṃdvaḥ
Ko2: dhaṃdva P, Pa: vaṃdvaḥ R: vedhaḥ
U: kramaḥ kra° A2: kramakrāmaṇa R: krama-
yogena 1 J1: °meṇe J1: vyojanaṃ Ko1, L, P,
Pa: yojanaṃ R: yojayet G: add śrīr astu

68

kuru karma yathā nyāyaṃ siddham bhavati tad rasam |
jārito mārītaś caiva punar jāritamārītaḥ |

Ko2: kurū A1: om P, Pa: yathānyāyaṃ
J1: nyāyaṃ Ko2: jñāya J1: siddhirbhavati
A2: taṃ J1: tādrśaṃ P: tadrasaṃ G: rasaḥ ||
Ko2: rasya 6o Ko2: om J1: ś J1: puna
B: jāritamā | J1: jārite mārīta R: jāritabhārītaḥ

69

daśasaṅkrāntiniṣkrāntaḥ koṭivedhī bhaved rasaḥ |

R: daśamaṃ 1 maṅkrān° J1: dasaṃkrāṃte-
nikrāṃtī Pa: daśasaṅkrāntinikrānto | Ko1: °ti-
nikrāṃto P: °ti nīkrāṃto A2: °niḥkrītaḥ
B: °niḥkāṃta L: °niṣkarāṃto G: °krāṃto
U: °krāṃtā A1, Ko2: om L: koṭivedhi G: °dhī-
bhavedrasaḥ | | J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: mahārasaḥ

ratnaghoṣa uvāca |

A1, A2, L G: ratnaghoṣa Ko1: ratnaghoṣa
Ko1: vācaḥ

70

sādhayitvā prayatnena koṭivedhī mahārasaḥ |
śārīreṇa vinā tat sarvaṃ bhavati niṣphalam |

Ko2: sādha_itvā A1: om A2: koṭivedham
Ko2: koṭīvidhī A2: mahārasaṃ Ko2: mahāra-
sa J1: add ghanam J1: uttama yena Ko2: sari-
reṇa Pa: yena L: śārīreṇaiva J1: add bhakṣita-

		mātreṇa Pa: add bhuktitamātreṇa G: vinād Ko2: vīnā R: vinai J1, Pa: om Ko1: va P: vi- naite ra B: om G: eva Ko2: deva R: tena A2, U: devasarvaṃ J1, Pa: naro Ko2: bhavaṃti A2, Ko2: niṣkalaṃ B, Ko1, L, P: niḥphalaṃ J1, Pa: vīryavān
nāgārjun'ovaca		A1, A2, B, J1, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, Pa, R, U G: nā- gārjuna uvāca
71		
kathayāmi na sandeho mārkaṇḍeyena yat kṛtaṃ dirghāyuh kārakaṃ bhūme rāsasiddhe rasāyane		Pa Ko2: kathayāmī U: kathayo _L mi A1: om A2: saṃdehaṃ P: mārtamḍayenamā° J1: mā- rtamḍe° B, G, Ko2, U: mārkaṇḍena Ko1, L: mārtamḍayena R: mārkaṇḍena U: add ca B, G, R: yathā Ko2: yatnakṛtaṃ J1: kṛta B: dī- rghāyu Ko2: dirghāyū P: dirghārghāyus A2: kamakaṃ J1, Ko1, L: kara P: karaḥ G, Ko1, L: bhūmo J1, P: bhūmau U: rāsasiddhi Ko2: rasāyano 6z
72		
śatapalam abhayānām akṣadhātryā tathaiva kvathitaṃ jalaṃ śatāṣṭau bhāgam aṣṭāv aśeṣam *		J1, Ko1, L: śataphalam Ko2: sata _L phalam P: śataphalam Pa: śataṃ phalam A1: om Ko2: ūbha° B: alayānām _L m L: amayānām U: ubhayā nāma akṣa° A2: akṣadhātryos G: pakvadhātryās Ko2: akṣūdhātrā R: cākṣadhātryās Ko1: tatheva _L A2, B, Ko1, Ko2, L, Pa, U: ca A2, G, R: kvathita B: kkathi- ta J1: ca thinaṃ Ko1, L, P: kathitaṃ Ko2: sa- kathita Pa, U: kathita A2, B, Ko2, R, U: jala J1: śaṣṭīṣṭau Ko2: satāṣṭo L: bhāgav J1, Pa: aśeṣitaṃ Ko1, L: aśoṣitaṃ Ko2: aśeṣa
		Parallels ▼
73		
ghṛtamadhusitayāḍhyaṃ vyoṣacitraṃ daśāṃśaiḥ rasapaladaśasiddhaṃ lohacūrṇaṃ mṛtaṃ ca *		R: hṛtamadhuśata gadyaṃ Ko1: dhṛtamadhu- sitayā yuktaṃ U: ghṛtadhṛtamadhurā B: °dhuśata rādyam G: °dhuśata _L saṃkhyām Ko2: °dhurādyam _L A2: °yāṭhām J1: °yā _L ,

P: °yā yuktaṃ Pa: °yā muktaṃ | A1: om
 J1: add yukta J1: vyoṣacitra Ko2: vyoṣacī-
 traṃ A2, B: daśāṃsai G: daśāṃsaiḥ
 J1: daśāṃśena Ko1, L, Pa: daśāṃsake
 Ko2: daśāṃsai P: daśāṃsasam̐ke R: daśāṃśe
 B: raśapa° G: rasaparada° L: °ladiśasiddhaṃ
 J1, Ko2: °dāsasiddhaṃ B: lohajīrṇa
 Pa: lohaṃ cūrṇaṃ A2: ṛtaṃ Pa: ghr̥taṃ

Parallels

74

girisutasamam abhraṃ kāntabhṛṅgaṃ viḍaṅgaṃ
 rāsahitasubhāvyam̐ tandulair bilvakāyaiḥ |*

Ko2: gīryūta° B, U: giriyuta° Pa: °sama R: gi-
 riyutaṃ masamamabhraṃ P: °samamabhraṃ
 J1: giri-₁sutaṃ samasacakābhṛṅgaṃ A1: om
 Pa: mantraṃ A2: abhraṃkāṃ° R: add kānta
 bhṛṃ Ko2: kita bhraṃgaṃ L: kāṃta bhṛṅgaṃ
 P: kāṃtabhṛṅgaṃ R, U: kāntabhraṃgaṃ
 Ko2: vīḍaṃ 64 Pa: vibhaṃgaṃ Ko1: °hitam
 ubhāvyam̐ Ko2: °tasūbhāvyam̐ P: °tamubhā-
 vyam̐ B, Ko1: taṃḍulai G, P, Pa: taṃḍulair
 Ko2: tuṃḍilaiḥ R: tāṃḍulair U: tuṃḍulair
 A2: vilvakājvaiḥ₁ B: vilvakākṣaiḥ | G: bilva-
 kākṣaiḥ | J1, Ko1, L, P: vilvakāṃjikaiḥ
 Ko2: bilvakā Pa: bilvakāṃjikaiḥ | 61 R: bilva-
 kābjaiḥ

Parallels

75

ahimarakatakalkam̐ lohapātreṇa māsam̐
 pratidinatanuśuddhaṃ kalkam̐ enaṃ variṣṭam̐ |*

R: ahisa|sakṛL ta° Ko2: aharasakṛtaculka
 A2: °raktatakalkam̐ B: °raktakalkam̐ J1: °ra-
 ktakṛtacūktam̐ Ko1, L, P: °raktakṛtacūktam̐
 Pa: °raktaklacūkta U: °₁rastutakalkam̐
 A1: om P: lohopā° B: lohapātra Ko2, R: loha-
 pātrastha A2: lohapātrasthamāsam̐ G: lohapā-
 tra₁māsam̐ U: lohapatrasthamāsam̐ | B: su-
 māsam̐ | R: māmam̐ R: mumṛtadita° B: supri-
 ditatuśuddhaṃ J1, L: sadinanatuśuddhaṃ
 Ko1, P, Pa: sadinanatusuddhaṃ Ko2: prati-
 dānatanasū₁dhaṃ U: °tanaśuddhaḥ A2,
 G: °śuddhaḥ B: kalka J1, Pa: kalkamenam̐

76

lihati śayanakāle vāmanetrārdhasevī
dhananibiḍasusandhir mattamātaṅgadarpaḥ |*

Ko2, U: etaṃ R: ava G: variṣṭhaṃ | | Ko2,
U: variṣṭāṃ Pa: cariṣṭaṃ |

Parallels ▼

Ko2: liṃhati R: lihi A1: om R: śatamaya°
Ko2: saya° B: śayati kāle Pa: śayakāle
Pa: sīma° Ko2: vāṃma° Ko1, L, P: mīma°
U: vāmanetrarddha° B: netrārdhasevā ||
G: vāmanetrāṅgasevī J1: mīnānetrārthasevī
R: vāmanebhrāvamevī | L A2, B: ḡhana°
G: dhana_L niviḍa° J1: ghananibiḍasusāṃdha
Ko1, L: dhananiviḍasusāṃdhe Ko2: ḡhaṃna-
nibiḍasidhe P, Pa: ghananiviḍasusāṃdhe
R: ghananiviḍasugandhi U: dhananiviḍasusi-
ddhe A2: mattamātaṅgadaryyo J1: matta-
mātaṅgadarppa Ko1, L: mattamātaṅgada-
rppā Ko2: matamātaṅgadarppā R: matamā-
taṅgadarppaṃ B: °darppa P, Pa, U: °darppā

Parallels ▼

77

vigatasakaladoṣaḥ sarvadigdivyacakṣuḥ |
madana iva sukāntiḥ kāmīnāṃ pravāraḥ |*

Pa: °kalaṃ doṣaḥ Ko2: °doṣa A1: om U: sa-
rvadikdivya° L, P, Pa: sarvadig divya° G: sa-
rvadigdivya° A2: sarvadig vidavya°
Ko2: sarvadikdivyacakṣu R: °gdivācakṣaḥ
G: sukāṃ_L tiḥ J1: sukāti Ko1, L, P: sukāṃti
Ko2: sūkāṃti R: mukānta R: kvāmi_L mi° J1,
Pa: kāmīnā Ko1, L: kāmīnāṃ
Ko2: kāmmanīnaṃ G: priyaś J1: pracārāḥ
Ko1, L, P: pravārāḥ Ko2: pravānaḥ Pa: praca-
rāḥ | R: pravīro U: pravānaḥ G: add ca |

Parallels ▼

78

jalada iva cāyuṣmān kuñcitāgrāgrakeśaḥ |
turaga iva viśuddhaḥ satkaviś citrakārī |*

B: jalana R: jvana A1: om Pa: ica Pa: add va
R: ma yuṣ° A2, G, J1, Ko1, L, P, U: ca yuṣ°

B: yuṣmān Ko2: ca yuṣmāmna Pa: yuṣmā
 G: kuṁcitās cāgrākeśāḥ J1: kuṁcitāgnāgrake-
 śā Ko1, P: kucitāgrāgrakeśāḥ Ko2, U: kuṁci-
 tāyāgrakeśān B: °keśān L, Pa: °keśāḥ R: °keśā
 Ko1: uraga J1: dhava G: śuddha J1: viśuddha
 Ko2: viśuddha A2: sakaviś Ko2: satkavī
 R: sākṣa vai U: satkaviś J1: catrakārī Ko2: cī-
 trakārī

Parallels ▼

79

vṛṣabha iva viceṣṭim abhragambhīraghoṣaḥ|
 suragaja iva loke śrāntadantāsu nityam |*

Ko2: vṛṣabha G: vṛṣabhasamagatir
 A2: vṛṣa_Lbhagativi° B: vṛṣabhagativiṣṭhīm J1,
 Ko1, P: vṛṣabhagativiceṣṭo L: vṛṣabhagativi-
 veṣṭo Pa: vṛṣabhagati_Lvicesṭā R: vṛṣabhaga|
_Ltiviciṣṭī A1: om G: vai Ko2: vicesṭā R: mātra
 gam° A2: agragambhīraṣoyah J1: abhrakāṁ
 gambhīraghoṣa Ko1: abhrakāṁ gabhīgho-
 ghaḥ Ko2: meghaghambhīragoṣa L,
 Pa: abhrakāṁ gambhīraghogaḥ P: abhra-
 kāṁ gabhīraghogaḥ B: °ghoṣaḥ Ko2: sūraga-
 jam R: turaga U: suragajam Ko2: iva R: dra
 G: śadam° A2, B: śrāntahantāsu Ko2: snāta-
 hantāsū R: śrāntahantās tu U: snātahantās
 tu J1: śrāntadamtam sunityam Pa: nitya|

Parallels ▼

80

prabhavati khalu loke candratārkaḥjivī ||*

Ko2: prabhavatu U: prasavati G: atha A1: om
 Ko2: śalū U: śalu G: golabamḍhanam āha ||
 Ko2: °rkaji vī 67

Parallels ▼

[Golabandha]

81

punar anyam pravakṣyāmi golakam bandham uttamam|
yena bhakṣitamātreṇa bhaven nara 'jarāmarah|*

Ko2: pūnyar A2: anya G: anyat J1: ratnam
Ko2: avya A1: pravakṣāmi Ko2: pravakṣāmī
A1: golabam... Pa: goḷam A2, B, R: gola-
vamḍhanam G, Ko1, L, P: golabamḍhanam
J1: golavamḍha Pa: va A1: om J1: vaciḷ tra-
kam Ko2: ūtama R: utumam Pa: om Ko2,
U: tena J1: om R: bhāṣita° Ko2: bhakṣita°
Pa: vibhitram A2, B, G, Ko1, L, P, R: om
Ko2: bhava Pa: ca| J1: vaprasupūm ca Ko2,
U: nara Pa: ...prasuptam ca A2, G: add syād B,
R: add bhavaty Ko1, L, P: bhavati A2, B, G,
R: aja° J1, Pa: jalodare Ko1, L, P: vīryavān
Ko2: jarāmara 68 U: jārāmarah||

Parallels ▼

82

gandhābhrakāntasahitam bhānuratnāni kāñcanam|
samajīrṇarasendrasya bandham kṛtvā tu golakam |*

G: gaṃdhakābhra° Ko1, L, P, Pa: gaṃdhakā-
bhrakāmtam sa° J1: gaṃdhakābhrakāmsa°
Ko2: °ta sahītam R: °ta sahītam A1: om
Ko2: bhāmnūratnāri A2, U: °tnāri B, G: °tnā-
di J1: kācanam Ko2: kaṃcanam Ko2: sama-
jīrṇa° J1: samajīrṇe ra° A2, Ko1, L, P, Pa,
R: samajīrṇam ra° Ko2: sūbamḍham
L: bamḍha U: subamḍham
J1: vamḍhaḷ kṛdbhānugālakam Ko1,
P: bamḍhakṛdbhānugolakam Pa: kṛdbhā
A2: kṛtasānugolakam 28 ḷ Ko2: kṛtagolaḷ ka
69 L: kṛṣṇānugolakam | U: kṛtagolakam|| G,
Pa: nu

Parallels ▼

83

rasendram pañcalohāni samabhāgāni lepayet|
saptapañcōttarās caiva yavās tu golakasya ca |*

A2: rasendre G: rasendraḥ J1, Pa,
U: rasendra A1: om A2: °gān ime A2: layet B,
G, R, U: melayet Ko2: prelayet L: saprapañ°
G: saprapam° Ko2: °cotarā R: °cotarās
J1: °ttarōs Ko1: yuvā Ko2, L, P: yavā
R: yāvāms B, Pa: yavāsu J1: yavāmu U: yavā-
stu A2: tur Ko2: om Ko1, L, P: sugo°
Ko2: sūgo° R: tu

Parallels ▼

84

ayo 'pi yad dhemaśaśiprabhākaram
karambitaṃ sūtakaajātagolakam |*

J1 Ko2: payopī Pa: ayāpi A1: om Ko2: om
R: dvaś Pa: yaddama° U: yuddhe mama sasi-
pra° G: baddhemaśaśīpra° P: hema° Ko2: sū-
dhe mama sasīpra° A2: dhemaśaśīpra° B: vi-
sasīprabhāraka R: ca śaśīprabhākāraṃ₁
L: °pramākāṃ, B: karaṃvitāṃ G: karaṃ
citaṃ Ko1: karaṃ vitaṃ Ko2: karabītaṃ
P: karaṃvitāṃ R: karambhitāṃ R: mūta°
B: sūtasūtagolaka U: °jānū|| golakaṃ A2: °ta-
kolakaṃ Ko2: °laka₁

Parallels ▼

85

narasya vakṣaṣtham idaṃ rasāyanam
rasāyanam cāmaratāṃ ca kārakam |*

Ko2: tarasya A1: om B, J1, P, Pa: vakṣastham
G: cakṣustham Ko1: vakṣyastham
R: vakṣasyam U: vṛkṣastham
Ko2: vṛkṣasthamā B: om J1: rasāyanaḥ
Ko2: rasāya R: ramāyanam U: rasāyana J1,
Ko1, L, P, Pa: om Ko2, R, U: rasāyana B, G,
U: cāmaratā J1: vāmaratā va Ko1, L, P, Pa,
R: vāmaratā Ko2: cāṃmaratā G: pra J1: tāva
U: va Ko1, L, P, Pa: add tāva G: dāyanam| |

Parallels ▼

86

sugandhalepatāṃbūlaṃ karpūraṃ kuṅkumāgurum|
śrīkhaṇḍaṃ mṛganābhīś ca kaṅkolaṃ jātikāphalaṃ ||*

Ko2: sūgaṃdhaṃle° A2: °le patāṃ vūlaṃ
R: °lepānāṃmūlaṃ U: °palatāṃbujaṃ
B: °tāṃmūlaṃ J1: °būla A1: om U: karpuraṃ
L: karpūrakum° G: karpūrakumkumāguru₁
B: kuṃkumāgaruṃ | Ko2: kukamāṅgūru
J1: °guru A2, L: śrīśaḍaṃ B, R: śrīkhaṇḍa J1,
Ko1, P, Pa, U: śrīśaḍaṃ Ko2: śrīśaḍa
J1: mṛgabhāspi Ko2: mṛganābhaṃ J1: om
R: kākolaṃ J1, Ko1, L, P: kaṃkolajā° A2: jāti-

kāpalaṃ 31 R: jātikaphalaṃ

Parallels ▼

87

sugandhāni dravyāṇi khānapānāni yāni ca
bhuktisthānāni sarvāṇi krameṇaitāni sasya ca |*

B, R, U: sugaṃdhānyāni G: sugaṃdhīni
Ko2: sūgaṃdhānyāni Pa: sugaṃdhānyaLni
A1: om A2: anyadra° J1: dravyāni Ko2: dra-
vyāṇiṃ A2, U: śāna° Ko1, L, P, Pa: khānipā°
Ko2: śāṃnapāṃnāni G: °nādi R: °nāyāni
G: kāni L: yā navi P: yāni Ko1: yānīva B: tu | L,
R: om P: va A2, G: mukti° U: muktāsthā°
J1: bhuktinīni Ko1, P: bhuktisthānīni
Ko2: muktāsthāṃnāni L: muktisthānīva
J1: sarvāṃṇi Ko1, L: krameṇai° B: krameṇai-
vāni G: krameṇaiva R: krameṇaiva narasya
A2, G, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: rasasya B: rasasya
Ko2: śasya

Parallels ▼

88

yasyāgra kuñcitāḥ keśāḥ śyamā vai padmalocanā |
vistīrṇaṃ jaghanaṃ yasyāḥ saṅkīrṇaṃ hṛdayaṃ bhavet |*

A2, Pa: yasyāgre G: yasyāgrāḥ Ko1: yaśpāgra
R: yasyāya U: yasyāgrā A1: om R, U: kuñcitā
G: kuñcitākeśāḥ J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: kucivīkeśā
Ko2: tucitākesā R: kveśāḥ U: keśaśyāmā A2,
B, G, Ko2, Pa, R: śyamā J1: śpamā
Ko1: śamā L: gamā P: śamād G: vā G: pa-
dmapalo° L: pasalo° A2, Ko2: °cana
R: °canāḥ G: ivi° Ko1: vāstīrṇaṃ Ko2: vi-
stīrṇaṃ L: āstīrṇaṃ P: vāstīrṇaṃ Pa: vī-
stīrṇaṃ B: om A2: vadanāṃ Ko2: jaghanyaṃ
G, J1, Ko2, Pa, U: yasya Ko1, P: yasyā
Ko2: saṅkīrṇaṃ L: saṅkīrṇa R: om
Ko2: hṛdayaṃ L: ladayaṃ J1: navat

Parallels ▼

89

kṛṣṇapakṣe bhaved yasyā yuvatyaḥ puṣpadarśanam |

J1, Pa: kṛṣṇānakṣe Ko1: kṛṣṇā bhakṣe

kākinī sā samākhyātā uttamā ca rasāyane |*

P: kṛṣṇabhakṣe A1, B, R: om Ko1, Pa: bhave
P: bhavedyasyā J1, Ko2, U: yasya A2, G: yu-
vyāḥ J1: yu₁vatpā Ko2: yūvyā J1: puṣpha-
darśana Ko2: pūphadarsanaṃ J1: kāminā
Ko1, P, Pa: kāminī L: kāminīm L: ā J1: samā-
khyāta Ko2: samāśyātā Ko2: utamā A2, L: ra-
sāyena

Parallels ▼

90

āliṅgane ca vaktavye sparśane ca suśobhane|
maithūne mardane caiva surūpā vāmalocanā |*

G, L: āliṅgena Ko2: ālaṅgane A1, B, R: om
J1: ka-₁rttavye G: darśane J1: sparśena
Ko2: parsanaṃ J1: om P: va Ko1: vasu°
A2: suśobhanāḥ L G: suśobhanā|| J1: suśo-
bhanai Ko2: sūsobhane L: suśobhaje|
Ko2: maithūne Ko2: sūrāpā U: surāpā
Ko2: vā vilocanā 76 | L U: vā vilocane||

Parallels ▼

91

vālmīkaṃ mukharogaṃ ca cakṣuṣrotrādināśikā|
kaphapittānilair bhuktā svabhāvaguṇabhūṣitā |

A2, G, Ko1, L, P: vālmīkaṃ B, R: vālmīka
A1: om J1: mu₁mu° A2: mukharo₁ bhāgaṃ B,
R: mukhabhāgaṃ Ko2: mūṣarogaṃ
U: muṣarogaṃ Ko2: cakṣūśrotādi°
U: cakṣuśrotādi° A2: cakṣuśrotrādināśikāṃ
J1: cakṣuśrotradi nāśikā Ko1, L, P,
Pa: cakṣuśrotrādināśikā B: °nāśakaṃ ||53
G: °sikāṃ|| R: cakṣudśrotrādināmakam vāta-
pittānalo A2: °ttānalaī J1, Ko2: °nilai A2: yu-
ktāṃ G, J1, Ko1, P, Pa: bhaktā Ko2: bhūttkā
L: bhatkāra R: bhuktā J1, Ko1: add ra J1,
Ko1: ca bhā° Ko2: svabhāvaguṇabhūṣita 77
L: ca bhāvaguṇamūṣitā | R: mubhāva-
gu₁ṇabhāṣitam A2: °bhūmitāṃ 36 B: °ṣitam |

92

udambaraṃ ca citraṃ ca prasuptaṃ ca jalodare|

Pa A1: om A2: udamvaram B: adambara
G: udambaram J1: u₁damvaram R: om A1: va
A2: caś J1: rasaḥ B: tvamtram J1: śarireṇa

grāhiṇī durnāmakam gulmaṃ gaṇḍamālā śilās tathā |

J1: va J1: sarvaṃ Ko2: prasūtaṃ J1: bhavati
A2, B, Ko2: jalodaraṃ J1: niḥphalaṃ

nāgārjunovāca

R A2, B, U: grahaṇī G: grahaṇārśas tathā
Ko2: grahaṇi Pa: om Ko2: dūrnā° A2: 1 durnā-
ma G: om A1: gutvaṃ J1: gutva Ko1, L, P: gu-
lvaṃ Ko2: golamaṃ Ko2: jūḍa° U: jaḍa°
A2: gaṇḍamā J1: gaṇḍhamālāśilāstathā
A2: śilā G: śivās Ko2: śilās P: tatathā

A1, A2, B, G, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, R, U: om Pa: nā-
gārjunauvāca

93

etaiḥ sarvair vinirmukto valipalitavarjitaḥ |
śatāni trīṇi varṣāṇi jīved vai karivikramaḥ |*

A1, J1, Ko1, Ko2, P: etai A1, A2, J1, Ko1,
P: sarvai Ko2: sarve1 Pa: sarveḥ Ko2: vini-
rmukto A2, R, U: valīpa° G: valīpalitavīrtaḥ||*
Pa: °libhavarjinaḥ | 66 A1, J1, Ko1, L, P: °ta-
vīryasaḥ Ko2: °rjita Ko2: satāni A1, J1, Ko1,
P, Pa: trīṇi Ko2: traṇava° A2: varyāṇī G,
U: varṣāṇāṃ A2: jāve Ko2, U: jīve A1, B, L,
Pa: jīvedvai J1: jīvaidvaika° G: ca Ko2: cai
R: om U: caika° A2: dvaika° R: kesari°
Pa: kaṃri° G: hari° B: karavikramaḥ |
Ko2: kārivikrama 79

Parallels ▼

94

dhṛtaṃ yugaṃ mukhe yasya guṇāya samudāhṛtaṃ |*

A1, G, J1, Ko1, L, P: dutaṃ A2: hṛtaṃ B, Pa,
R: drutaṃ U: dataṃ B, R: yuga G: pūgaṃ
Ko2: yūgaṃ B, R: mukho Ko2: mūṣe
Ko2: guṇāya B: guṇā yasya udāhṛtaṃ ||56
R: guṇaṃ yasya udāhṛtaṃ Ko1: samudāha-
taṃ1 Ko2: syamūdāhūtaṃ Pa: sābhra-
dāhṛta | 67

Parallels ▼

95

atha ṣoḍaśapūrṇāni golakāni narottame |
dhṛtāni mukhamadhye tu teṣu vakṣyāmi ye guṇāḥ |*

Ko2: ṣoḍaśapū° A1, J1, Ko1, L, Pa: kolakāni
P: kolakānirottamaḥ A1: rottamaḥ A2, R: na-
rottamaḥ G: surottame|| J1: narottamaḥ
Ko1: rokṣame Ko2: nirotame 8o L: naśetta-
maiḥ| A1, Ko1, L: hutāni A2, B, G, Pa: drutāni
J1: dutāmni P: du₁tāni R: śrutāni U: datāni
R: sukha° A2: śukha° A1, J1, Ko1,
P: muṣamadhye Ko2: mūṣamadhe Ko2: ta B,
P: vakṣāmi Ko2: yakṣā₁mī U: vikṣāmi J1: yo
Ko2, U: je R: yā J1: guṇā Ko2: gūṇā R: nāṇān

Parallels ▼

96

nāsau chidyate śastraiś ca pāvakena na dahyate|
vāyuvego mahātejā śakratulyo mahāyaśaḥ |*

A2: nāsau J1: nāṃsau P, R: nāmau A1, Ko1,
L, P: chiṃdate A2, U: chidyati B, R: chidyamti
G: bidyati J1: biṃdate Ko2: chīdyatī
Pa: biṃdamte A1: śastreś J1: śāstre-₁ś L: śa-
straiva Ko1: om A1: pācakena B: pātakena
G: pāva₁ena Ko2: naṃ B, U: dahyati J1: da-
kyate Ko2: dyahate 8i R: ruhya A2: vāyutego
Ko2: lālavego U: lāghavego A2, R, U: mahāte-
jāḥ B: mahātejo R: cakra° B: śakratulya
Ko2: śakratulo B, R: mahārasaḥ Ko2: mahā-
ya₁sā U: mahāśayaḥ||

Parallels ▼

97

trailokye ca manohārī kāmadeva iva sthitaḥ|
icchayā jāyate tasya tādrśo jāyate tvayā

Ko2: triloke L: trailodhye R: tailokye Pa: trai-
lokya₁va A2: nayano° B: mahāvārī | Ko2: ma-
nohārī R: mahākārī Ko2: kāmmadeve U: °va-
chaviḥ Ko2: add ca G: samaprabhaḥ||
Ko2: chabī R: puri U: om G: om Ko2: smṛtaṃ
8z U: smṛtaḥ₁|| B: ichā L: innayā R: iśchā B,
R: add vā G: om A1, J1, P: śadrśo A2,
B: sadrśyo G: drśyo Ko1, L: sadrśo
Ko2: tādrśo Pa: ktādrśye R: śuddhaś R: add
co G: icchayā G: add khegatir A2, Ko2, U: cha-
yā G: bhavet| | L: nnayā R: śchayā

98

tasya sparśanamātreṇa sarvalohāni kāñcanam|
sakalā niṣkalāś caiva jivec caṃdrārkatārakau||*

A2: om J1: śparsana° R: saṃmparśamā°
Ko2: saṃ_Lsarsamā° B, U: saṃsparśamā°
P: °treṇe Ko2: °hānī Ko2: kañcanam 83
B: sakalo G: niṣphalā A1, J1, Ko1, L, P,
Pa: om G: abhicārāḥ Ko2: niṣkalā U: add cai-
va saceto somakāṃto B: caiva...nya||6o
save_Lto samakāṃtā ca | G: syuḥ R: add sthūla-
sūkṣmarasāyanam sarvata_Ls somakāntā ca
G: jīved Ko2: jive R: jived R: add ā G: caṃdra-
rkatārkaṃ | B: °rakai || R: °rakam

Parallels

Notes

[Sūtakālāntagabandha]

99

punar anyam pravakṣyāmi bandham suravarārcitam |
sūtakālāntakam bandham yad uktam parameṣṭhinā|
hīnāṅgo hy adhikāṅgāś ca savyādhiḥ kubjavāmanah |*

G: add atha sūtakālātāṃtakabaṃdhamāha||_L
J1: ratnam Ko2: anya Ko2: pravakṣāmi A2: vi-
dhiṃ Ko2: baṃdha R: vaṃdyaṃ G: add su-
kharārcitam|| atha sūtakālātāṃtakabaṃdha-
māha||_L B: susu° R: sukharā°
Ko2: sū_Lkhamrā° G: punar anyam pra-
vakṣyāmi bandham sukharā° A2: sukharācci-
tam L: sukharārcitāḥ | P, Pa: sukharārcitā A1,
J1: °rcito Ko1: °rcitā G: sūtakālātāntakam J1,
Ko2: sūtakālamtagam Ko1, L: sūtakālātagam
P, Pa, U: °tagam B, R: gaṃdham J1: vaddham
Ko2: badham J1: yud Pa: yed Ko2: ūktam A2,
L, R: parameṣṭhinā B: utpanā || J1: para-
meṣṭinī Ko1: parameṣṭitā Ko2: parameṣṭinām
P: parameṣṭitānā J1: hīnāṅgye A1: hīnāṅge
Ko1, P: hīnāṅgo Ko2: hināṅge L: hīnām'śo
J1, Pa: om R: ḥrdhikāṅgasya Ko2, Pa: om a°
A1: adhikāṃ_Lgave J1: adhikāṅgam
Ko1: adhikāṅgacchi L: achikāṅgāś B: adhi-
kāṅgasya P: add ci A1: va Pa: caiva | J1: add
vaLsvā A1, Ko1, P: svāsavān B: savyādhaḥ
G: savyādhi J1: sarvān Ko2, U: savyā L,
Pa: khāsavān R: sa vyādhaḥ Ko2, U: add ca
A1: kuṣṭavāmanā 23 A2: kujjavāmanah _L
B: kuṣṭavāmanah ||62 J1: kuṣṭavān Ko1,
P: kuṣṭavāmanah Ko2: kubjavāṃmana 85 L,

100

gatendriyo nā nayano jarā grasto jitendriyaḥ |
jaḍas ca gadado mūko gatihānas tathaiva ca |*

101

aśaṅkatraya vinirmukto jīvaśeṣe ca tiṣṭhati |
evaṃ bandhaprabhāvena samāvartto yadā bhavet |*

102

punar anyam bhavet piṇḍam nātra kāryā vicāraṇā |
pañcāmṛto mahāyogo hy ukto manthānabhairave |

Pa: kuṣṭhavāmanah R: kuvjavāmasanah

Parallels ▼

A1, Ko1, L, P, Pa: gatāṃdriyāṇi A2: gajāṃ hi
J1: nāgatāṃddhi G: gatāṃdhriyāṇi
Ko2: gatāṃgrīyāṃṇi R: gatāstriyāṇi
U: gatāṃdriyā B: gatāstriyāṇi A2: pāṇi
J1: pāṇinā A2: jurā Ko1, P: narā L: nagā
Pa: jara A1: gragrasto J1: grastā U: yateṃ°
J1: jineṃdviprah Ko2: jitaṃdriya B, R: jaḍa
J1: jaṃmaśca Ko2: jaḍasya A2: gadgado ḷ
B: gadgada R: ga...da U: gaḍgado
Ko2: gadūdomuko B: mū R: mūko pi A1: gati-
hāsas A2, G, Pa, R, U: gatihānas B: tihinaḷ
J1: gatihānis Ko2: gatihinaṃ B: stathaiva
B: caḥ ||63

Parallels ▼

G: aśaka° J1: abhraka° A1, A2, B, Ko1, L, P,
Pa, R: asaṃka° Ko2: asaṃkatrayādi
U: asiṃkatrayadi A2, G, R: om vi° Ko2: vini-
mukto Ko2: jiḷvase Pa: jīve śeṣe U: jīvasevye
R: va A2, B, J1, Ko1, P, R, U: tiṣṭhati
Ko2: ttiṣṭati A1, A2, B, G, J1, Pa, U: etad
Ko2: et t P: eḷva R: etadvandha pramāṇena
Ko1: draṃdha° A1, J1, L, P, Pa: gaṃdha°
B: baṃdhapramāṇena G: °veṇa J1: samāva-
rtte R: dayā

Parallels ▼

Ko1: pu na nā L: punaranyam Ko1: add r
B: om J1: atyam Ko2: anam R: anyadbhave-
tpiṇḍam Ko2: bhava B: avetpiṇḍam P,
U: bhavetpiṇḍam Ko2: tiḍam

103

[London] dārākṣasauḡavaṇeva punas tatraiva bhāṣitam |
nānetarahitam kiñcit trailokye sacaraḡhare |

J1: yimmaṃ_L nātra J1: kārya R: kāyā A1,
Pa: kāryavi° Ko2: kāryavicyāraṇā U: vicā-
raṇāṃṃṃ || Ko2: paṃcāṃ_L mṛto
U: paṃcāṃ_L Lpaṃto A2, B: mahāyoga
Ko2: mahāyogo Pa: mahāyogo | R: mahāyoge
U: mahāyogaḡ A1, G, J1: om L, P: hyukto
R: add cāraṇāmaya A1: dyukto B: om G: śru-
to_L J1: yukto R: nāśanam J1: mathā°
A1: saṃghātabhairave 26 A2: maṃt_L nabhai-
rave B: sajāmarāṇavināśanam |
Ko1: maṃyāta bhairave Ko2: methānabhaira-
vaṃ 88 L: saṃdhāta--bhairave | P: maṃthāta-
bhairave Pa: maṃthānabhairaLve R: om
G: °ravat |

A1, A2, B, J1, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, Pa, R, U: om
P: vārākṣasau ga° Ko1: vārākṣasaurāva°
A1: vārākṣasau rāva° A2: vīrākṣasauḡavaṇeva
B, R: haṃsapādīrasenaiva G: vīrākṣasaura-
veṇaiva J1: vārā-_L kṣaso rāvaṇe ca Ko2: vi-
rākṣasoraṇe|va Pa: vārākṣasoraṇenaiva |
U: vīrākṣasaura vai ve ṇaiva Ko2: pūna
J1: punastatraiva R: purastatraiva Ko1,
Ko2: tatveva Ko2: bhāṣitam U: nānena ra°
Pa: nāmena ra° R: nāṃnaivara°
Ko2: nāṃmenara° B: nāṃnaiva ra° A2: nāge
nara° Ko1: °ra hitam P: °hita Ko2: kiṃcī
P: kaṃcit R: kiṃ_L cittrailokya J1: trolke
Ko2: triloke_L R: add me A1, A2, B, G, J1, Ko1,
Ko2, P, Pa, U: sacaraḡcare R: carācare

104

[London] pṛthivyāpas tathā tejovāyurākāśam eva ca |
koṭivedhī mahārasaḡ grhyā piṃḡam koṣṭasu saṃyutam |

A1, A2, B, J1, Ko1, Ko2, L, P, Pa, R, U: om
Ko2: pṛthavyāpa A2, P, R, U: pṛthivyāpastathā
J1: pṛthivyāpastathātejo vāyurākāśameva
Ko2: stā B, P: tejo vā° A1, Ko1, Pa: tejo vāyur
ākāśam A2: tejovāyu_L r ākāśam Ko2: tejovāyū-
rākāśam U: tejo vāyurākāśameva L, R: °kāśa-
meva A2: koṭivedhīr G, Ko2: koṭivedha
U: koṭivedhaṃ B: °dhīrasagrahyam A1,
Ko1: mahārasa G, Pa: mahārasam Ko2,
U: rasam R: raso A2: asaṃgrāhya P: mahāra-
sagrhyā A1: mṛhyā B: om G: grāhya Ko2, Pa,

105

ekaikasya tu madhyasthaṃ guṭikāṃ kāraved budhaḥ |
guṭikāpañcamākhyātāḥ śaṣṭhaṃ jīvaṃ ca kevalam |

U: grāhyaṃ R: grāhyaḥ J1: mṛhyā₁pimṃmako°
A1: pimṃde Ko2: piḍa G, Pa: pimḍako°
Ko2: kāṣṭha R: kāṣṭu A2, Ko1: koṣṭasu-
samyutaṃ Ko2: sūsamyūtaṃ 90

U: ekaikastyanuma° Ko2: stanū Ko2: ma-
dhyastaṃ A1: graṭikāṃ B: guṭi₁kā
Ko2: guṭikāṃ Ko2: kārae A1, J1, U: kāraye-
dbudhaḥ Ko2: būdha A1, J1: guṭikāṃ paṃca-
mākhyātā A2: guṭikāḥ paṃ₁casamākhyātā
B: guṭikāyaṃ samākhyātā G: guṭikevasaptā-
khyātā Ko1: guṭikā paṃcamākhyātā
Ko2: guṭipecasamāsyātā L: guṭikā- paṃcamā-
khyā tāḥ Pa: guṭikāṣaitvam ākhyātā |
R: guṭikēyaṃ samākhyātā U: guṭipaṃcasamā-
khyātā P: °khyātā B: draṭhaṃ R: ḍaṣṭraṃ
J1: śaṣṭajīvaṃ Ko2: jīvaṃ J1: kevalaṣaḍ R: ke-
valā

106

[London] ṣaḍguṇaṃ pañcastho'lpasya tāmrayāṃ suśobhanam |
ūrdhvapurūṣamānaṃ tu puruṣārdhaṃ garbhamaṇḍale |

A1, A2, B, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa, R: om Ko2,
U: om Pa: ṣaṭguṇaṃ J1: guṇapaṃcastholya-
sya A1: paṃcastholasya B: pimḍiṣṭhalāsyā
G: pimḍarstho lpaṃ Ko1: paṃcastho lpasya
L: paṃcasthaulpasya Pa: pimḍasthaulasya
R: piṇḍasthūlaṃ ca A2: pimḍasthauyasyatā-
mra₁pātraṃ B, R: tāmrapātraṃ G: tāmrayā-
traṃ Pa: tāmraplaṃ Pa: ūdhaṃ pu° J1: va-
rddha-₁pu° G: ūrdhvaṃ pu° A2: urdhve pu°
A1: ūrdhapa° B: rddhapuruṣamātraṃ
R: ūrdhvaṃ puḍeraṣamātraṃ R: ca A1, B, J1,
Ko1: puruṣārdha G: puruṣārdhe
Pa: puruṣārdhaṃ R: dardhaṃ A2: garbha-
maṇḍalaṃ L: garbhamaṇḍale |
R: gaṇḍamaṇḍala₁m B, G: °ḍalaṃ

107

caturmukhaṃ kṛta koṣṭhaṃ tasyopari niveśayet |
goghṛtaṃ ca māṃ tailaṃ samabhāgāni melayet |

G: śrīLca° A2: ca₁rmukhaṃ B, R: caturmukha
Ko2: catumūrṣaṃ A1, A2, B, G, Ko1, Ko2, P,
Pa, R, U: kṛtaṃ A2, B, J1, Ko1, P, Pa, R,
U: koṣṭhaṃ A2: tasthopari Ko2: ni₁vesaet
A1: goghṛteṃea Ko2: gaughṛte R: om A1, J1,

108

pūrayitvā kuṭāhaṃ tu digdiśāpālapūjanam|
kumārīṃ pūjayet tatra gaṇapūjāṃ kusumas tathā |

Ko1, P: mā Ko2: mähā Pa: om A2, B, G,
U: mahātailaṃ L: māṃ..tailaṃ A1, J1, Ko1,
P: taila Ko2: telaṃ Ko1: °gā nimelayet

G: pūrayitva_L Ko2: pūriyītvā B: kaṭāhaṃ
J1: kaṭāha Ko2, U: kaṭāhe R: kaḍāhaṃ G: ca
Ko2: tū A2: tudikliśāṃ pā° B, Pa, R: digdiśo-
pā° G: daśadigpāla° Ko2: disgsāpālapūja-
naṃḥ A1, B, G, J1, P, Pa, U: kumārī A2: ku-
mārīḥ Ko2: kumārī_L R: ku_Lmāmri J1: pūjaye
Ko2: pūja_e A2: pūjayettra U: pūjayettatra
U: guṇa° Ko2: guṇapūjāṃ A1, Ko1: kusus A2,
G: guruṃ B: guru Ko2: gurus R: om J1: kuru-
stathā P: kusumastathā U: gurustathā|| R: add
kuru

109

caturdikṣu baliṃ dadyāt yathoktaṃ gurubhāṣitam|
dhamanaṃ tatra kurvīta caturdikṣu śanaiḥ śanaiḥ |

A1, Ko1: catudikṣu Ko2: caturdikṣaṃ
J1: valaṃ Ko2: balaṃ Ko2: tathoktaṃ U: ya-
thokta Ko2: sivabhā° A2, B, G, R, U: śivabhā°
A1, B: kuvvīta Ko2: kurvītaḥ R: kuvīta
U: kurvīti Ko2: catudikṣū R: caturdikṣa A2,
Ko1: śanai Ko2: sanai A1: śanai 2 34 R: śa-
naiśśanaiḥ J1, Ko1: śanai Ko2: sanai_L94L

110

sutaptaṃ ca vijānīyāt sṛṣṭībhū nirdhūmaṃ ca yathā bhavet|
candrārko ugraharakṣīrāśayo bhavanāni |

J1 Ko1: sutamaṃ Ko2: sūtaptaṃ Ko2: vijāni-
yāt A2, G: °yān B: °yā R: vijānīyānni° A2, G,
Ko2, U: om Pa: sṛṣṭīni° Ko2: nirdhumaṃ A2,
B, G, Ko2, R, U: yadā A2: caṃdrarkke
B: caṃdrārkkā Ko1, L: caṃdrarko Ko2,
U: caṃdrārke Pa: caṃdrārkaḥ G: caṃdrārkkā-
nugraho bhikṣārāśayo R: candrānkānugrahā-
ri|_Lkṣāmaṃśayo A2: tu grahā ṛkṣārāśayoḥ
B: ugraho bhikṣārāśayo Ko2: stū grahā-
rakṣārāśayo U: tu grahārirakṣārāśa_Lyo
Pa: °rakṣā 'rāśayo A1, Ko1, P: °kṣīrāśayo
Ko2: bhūva° A2, B, G, R, U: bhūva° A2, B, G,
Ko2, Pa, R, U: ca

111

namaskṛtya guruṃ devaṃ ātmānaṃ tatra nikṣipet|

A1: namaskṛtyaṃ J1: namastubhyaṃ

sudagdhaṃ taṃ vijānīyāt sṛṣṭibhūtaṃ niyojayet |

Ko2: add ta Ko2: gū ruṃ₁ J1: gurudevam
Ko2: deva B: devamātmānaṃ U: devaṃmā-
tmānaṃ G, Ko2, R: mātmanaṃ A1: tamtra
A2: tavraṣṭi J1: niḥkṣi° A2: nirṣapet 56 B,
R: gudaghraṃ G: gudadanaṃ Ko2, U: om
J1: ta B: °yā B: sṛṣṭirupaṃ G: sṛṣṭirūpaṃ
J1: sṛṣṭibhūvaṃ R: sṛṣṭi₁rūpaṃ R: niyojayat

112

kalalaṃ ca bhavet sarvaṃ punaś cāyaṃ viniṣipet |

J1: kalakaṃ Pa: kalala B, Ko2, R, U: om P,
Pa: bhavetsarvaṃ A2: punaścāpaṃ J1, P,
Pa: punaścāyaṃ Ko1: add raktavarṇaṃ vijānī-
yāt tejo tejā niyojayet

113

sudagdhaṃ taṃ vijānīyāt sṛṣṭibhūtaṃ niyojayet |
māṃsapiṇḍaṃ bhaved yatra vāyus tatraiva niṣipet |

A1, J1, Pa: raktavarṇa A2, G: raktavarṇaṃ
P: raktavarṇā B, Ko1, R: om Ko2, U: om
G: vijā° A1, J1, P, Pa: tejo tejā A1, J1, P,
Pa: om A2: teje tejo G: tejas tejāmsi yo°
A1: māṃsapiṇḍaṃ A2: māṃsapim J1: māsa-
pimḍa J1, L, P: bhavedyatra A2, B, G, R: tatra
R: vāyuṃ J1, P, Pa: vāyustatraiva B: tatreva
A2: vikṣipet 58

114

bhramaṃ ta hemasaṅkāśaṃ jīvatvaṃ tatra dāpayet |
kṛtvā tatra mahārāvaṃ ṛkāraṃ surapūjanam |

A2: abhram J1: bhramataṃ A1, Ko1: bhra-
maṃta A2: aṃtaṃ B, G, Ko2, R, U: taṃ
J1: om Pa: taddhema° R: hemamakāśaṃ G,
Ko2: °kāśaṃ B, G, R: jīvaṃ J1: jīvatva Ko2: ji-
vitvaṃ R: mudā° B: pradā° J1: dāpayat
Ko2: mabehārāva A1, J1: ṛkāraṃ A2: ṛkāraṃ
B: kuṃkuraṃ G: kukuraṃ Ko2: rnuṃkāra
Pa: ṛkāla R: oṃkāraṃ U: oṃkārasurapūji-
taṃ || A1, J1, Pa: sūra° A2, B, G, R: surapūji-
taṃ Ko2: sūra₁pūjitaṃ

115

uttiṣṭhati na sandeho pūrvāhne bhāskaro yathā |
divyatejo mahākāyo divyadṛṣṭir mahābalaḥ |

A2, B, Ko1, P, Pa, R: uttiṣṭhati J1: uttiṣṭamṭi
Ko2: utiṣṭati L: at tiṣṭhati U: uttiṣṭatīva
Ko2: va A2, R: saṃdehaḥ A2: pūrvān he
G: pūrvānhe J1: pūrvokte Ko2: pūrvavyo
L: pūrvāhena P: pūrvakte U: pūrve
R: bhā~~msa~~svaro A2, R: divyatejā J1: mahākā-

dṛśyate bhuvanam sarvam sa siddhidaḥ |
saptasiddheṣu ye siddhā vimānaṃ preṣayanti te |

yau G, Ko1, P, Pa: divyadrṣṭi Ko2: divyadrṣṭā
R: divyadrṣṭin A1, J1: divyadrṣṭima° A2,
U: divyadrṣṭirmahābalaḥ Ko2: mahābalā

Ko2: dṛśyate Ko2: bhūva₁naṃ P: sarvaṃ
A1: sasidha B, Pa: sasiddhaḥ J1: saṃsiddhi-
sarvasi° A2, G, U: add siddhaḥ Ko2: add si-
dha sarvasidhāda 98 R: siddham~~mas~~arvasi°
A1, A2, B, G, Pa, U: sarvasi° Ko2: saptasi-
dheṣu ye sidhā Ko2: add vimānaṃ preṣayanti
te 6 yojanavistiraṇaṃ ghaṇṭācāmara₁
bhūṣitaṃ 99 dipte hemammayam maṇira-
tneṣu sobhitaṃ saṃsakāhalanirghāṣairasya-
rogī tata vādibhī 10||₁. pūphamālā patākaiś
Ko2: add ca kiṃkiṇiravamaṇḍitaṃ sidhaṃ
mayūtakaṃnyānāṃ sa Ko2: add sapā-
saṭavihvalā 1 divyābharanastraṃ₁ ni divya-
pūspāṇi yāni ca āgachanti na J1: sarve si-
ddhiṣu Ko2: saṃdeho ādeśo deva divyatam 2
grahitvā sādhakendram tu B: go Ko2: siddha-
lo₁ ke Ko2: add vrajanti te saṃnapānāni di-
vyāni divyāni bhūvanāni ca 3 ramaṇte
Ko2: add satahasraṃ tu divyakanyāṃ
Ko2: anekadhā Ko2: add kāṃ₁ mena J1: vi-
māna Ko2: vijalās tatra maṇmathena ma-
hotkaṭā 4 tasmāin ekārṇava Ko2: add ghore
naṣtai sthāvarajamgame devā Ko2: yatra vi-
liyaṃte Ko2: add sa si₁ dhastatra Ko2: liyate 5
R: add ardhayojanavistiraṇaṃ ghaṇṭācāmara-
bhūṣitam dīpta₁ dehamahayaṃ divyaṃ
maṇi₁ ratnaissugoṣitaṃ saṃkhalahari-
rghoṣaigrapasaro gītavādibhiḥ puṣpamālā pa-
tākā ca kiṃkiṇiravama₁ ṇḍitaṃ mi~~s~~siddha-
saṃyatakanyānāṃ sutūpā madavihvalā divyā-
bharanastraṃ₁ ni divyapūspāṇi yāni ca
ā₁ gaśchanti na sandeha...deśo deva divyatam
grhītvā mā~~s~~sādhakendram tu siddhalokaṃ
vrajanti te divyāni ~~vā~~khāna₁ pānāni divyāni
bhavanāni ca rasate śatasahasraṃ divyaka-
nyāmanekadhā kāmena vihvalāstatra
ma~~s~~asa₁ nmathā ma~~s~~sadanotkayaḥ tam~~mi~~ssi~~n~~ne-
kāṇave ghore naṣta~~m~~thā~~s~~thā₁ varajamgame
devā yatra viliyante siddhastatra vilī₁ yate

ratnaghoṣovāca |
117

bhūtakālāntakaṃ bandhaṃ yadā kartuṃ na śakyate |
anenaiva śarīreṇa kathaṃ siddhir bhaviṣyati |

L

A2, B, G, Pa: sūta° J1: bhūtakālāntakaṃ R: kā-
lāntakāya P: °kaṃ₁ baṃdhaṃ A2: vadhaṃ
R: vandhāya J1: karttu Ko2: kartū R: kaṃtuṃ
Ko2: sakate J1: anyeneva Ko2: anainaiva
Pa: ananaiva Ko2: sarireṇa Ko2: sidha₁ R: si-
ddhinbha° J1, L, P, Pa, U: siddhirbhaviṣyati
Ko2: bhaviṣyati 6

[Khecarabandha]

nāgārjuno'vāca |

118

punar anyam pravakṣyāmi khecaraṃ bandham uttamaṃ |
yena bhakṣitamātreṇa surasāmānyatā bhavet |

A2, L

Ko2: pūnar J1: punaratnaṃ G: anyat
Ko2: aṇa Ko2, R: pravakṣāmi A2: khe caraṃ
Ko2: baṃdhamūtaṃ J1: vaṃdhumuttam
U: baṃdhamutta₁ maṃ || Ko2: om A2: me₁ na
Ko2: bhakṣīta° B: su₁ rasāmatahātā Ko2: sura-
sāṃmaṃnatā R: °mā₁ kṛtā Pa: °nyato

119

yavena vindhate tāraṃ nāgaṃ sulvāyasaṃ sitam |
tadā tasya prakartavyaṃ ratnasamskāram uttamam |

A2: yāvan na B, G: yenaiva J1, Pa: yatnena
Ko2, U: yāvaṃ na R: yaivaina A2: vedhane G,
U: vidhyate J1: vedhate Ko2: vidhate R: vi-
ndate J1: tāra G: nā₁ ge A2, R: śulvā° G: śulvā-
yase A1, P: sulvāya saṃsitam B, Pa: sulvāya
saṃsthitaṃ J1: sulnnāya sasti₁ ta Ko2: sūlvā-
ya saṃcitaṃ U: śulbāya saṃcitaṃ || Ko2: tta-
sya J1: prakittivyam Pa: ra₁ tatna° J1: ratna-
saskāram Ko2: °skāramūtamaṃ 8 R: °skāra-
mutamam

120

indranilaṃ mahānilaṃ māṇikyaṃ mauktikaṃ tathā
padmarāgaṃ tathā vajraṃ marakatamatam aṣṭamam |

Ko2: idranila U: iṃdranila Ko2: mahānila
U: mahānila G: māṇikāṃ₁ Ko2: māṃṇi₁ kya
G: proktikaṃ Ko2: mūktikaṃ J1, Ko2: pa-
dmarāga B, Pa: vajaṃ R: vajra A1: marakaṃ
ta° A2: maLrakatam G: marakatam uktam

Ko2: margajamarkam Ko1: °mata B: maraka-
 jammarkamaṣṭamaṃ | Pa: marakamarka-
 maṣṭamaṃ | | 95 R: markajāmasankamaṣṭam
 m U: margajāḥ L karmamaṣṭamaṃ | J1,
 P: °matamaṣṭamaṃ A2: add arkkam
 Ko1: ṣṭamaṃ U: add asyā |

Ratnarāgajāraṇa

121

athātaḥ sampravakṣyāmi ratnarāgasya jāraṇam |
 puṣpe kākaśiro grhya apūrvamalasamyutam |

B: adātaḥ Ko2: yathāta R: athā-
 taṃsmaṃ pra° B: sapra° A2: sampravakṣyāmi
 Ko2: sampravakṣāmi B: ratnarāgaś ca
 J1: jāraṇa Ko2: jārakamḥ B, Ko2: puṣpa
 R: puṣpaṃ A2: puṣpakākāśiraṃ G: puṣpakāśi-
 sakaṃ Pa: puṣpekākaṃ siro A1, P: kākaśiro
 B: kākaśira Ko2: kākasira R: kāṣamaṣanaṃ
 U: kākaśiraṃ J1: kāmkaśirodahya apū-
 rvaṃma° G, U: grāhyaṃ apū° P: grhya apū-
 rbama° A1: grtya apūrvam ala° Ko2: grāhyaṃ
 yapūrvammalasamyūtaṃ 10 Pa: grhyaṃ |
 apūrvamatamsayutaṃ | R: grhyamapū-
 rvaṃmalamasamyūtam

122

rāśipūrvavidhānasthaṃ pūjayitvā tu pācayet |
 anena viḍayogena hemakulīśajāraṇam |

B A1: rāśipūrvam viṣānyasthaṃ A2: rāśipū-
 rvaṃ viśāṇaḥ sthaṃ G: śāśipūrvam J1: rāśipū-
 rvaṃ viśāṇaḥ sthaṃ Ko2: rāśipūrvā ca
 visāsthaṃ P: rāśipūrbaviḥhānasthaṃ Pa: rāśi-
 pūva viṣānasthaṃ | R: rāśipūrvam viśāla-
 sthaṃ U: rāśipūrvam ca viśasthaṃ
 Ko1: °vidyānasthaṃ G: add viśālākhyam
 Ko2: pūja_itvā R: nu Ko2: pāṃca° R: pācayet
 Ko2: yanena Pa: anenavi° U: biḍa°
 Ko2: viḍamvayo° R: hemaṃ ku°
 G: hemaṃku° Ko2: hemaṃ kulāṃsijāraṇam
 11 U: hemaṃ kulāśijāraṇam |

123

tejāsanasya lomāni dahyate bhūtavahninā |
 marīci suputrasya kavakarṇam tu yatpayah |

A2: tejo 'śanasya G: tejomayasya R: tājāmana-
 sya Ko2: °nasa G: loḥ hāni Ko2: lomāni B: add
 dagdhā vai A1, J1, Ko1, P, Pa: dagdhate
 A2: dagdhvā B: om G: dahed Ko2: dagdhvāvai

124

sa ca tasya dine grāhyaṃ taccūrṇāṃta na bhāvayet |
pādena tasya dātavyaṃ rasamūrdhni śiṣodbhavam |

R: dagdham₁ U: dagdhavair R: add vai G: vai-
bhū^o A2: vaibhūtabanhinā Ko2: bhūta-
vaṃnīnaṃ L: bhūtavihniṇā || B, R: marici
Ko2: maricī U: mirīci G: marīcisūtapu^o
A2: marīcisutapu^o Ko1, Pa: sūpu^o J1: srpu^o
B: sutapu^o Ko2: sūtapatrasya P: sūputrakasya
R: śatapattrasya U: sutapatrasya P: om ka^o
A1, Pa: kacakarṇaṃ A2: kaṃcukarṇaṃ
B: kaṃḍākarṇaṃ G: kaṃcukiṃ J1: kacaka-
varṇaṃ Ko2: kubhakarṇe R: kāṇḍūkarṇaṃ
U: kuṃbhakarṇe G: nyāstu A2, Ko1: yat
payah Ko2, U: yatnathā

125

asya pūrṇāvidēśreṣṭhaṃ sarvaratnasya melakam |
jārayet sarvayogena maṇirāgasya jāraṇam |

G: tac R: kaṃ B: satva Pa: satvaṃ Ko2, U: su-
vratasya A2: tv R: maṣaṇ A2: aṃtasya A2: di-
ggane Ko1, P: dite A1, B, G, Pa, U: taccūrṇaṃ
A2: taccūrṇāṃ Ko1: tac cūrṇāṃ ta Ko2: ta-
cūrṇaṃ J1: taccūrṇe tena P: taccūrṇaṃ tana
R: taścūrṇaṃ tena A1, A2, B, G, Ko2, Pa,
U: tena Ko2: bhāva_et R: bhā₁ Lyet B: stasya
P: dātavyaṃta B: rasamūrdhe Ko2: ra-
syamrdhi P: rasamūrdhi Ko1: rasamūrdviśi^o
A2, L: °rddhniśiṣodbhavaṃ A1: rdhniśi^o
B: mūkhodbhavaṃ | G: śikhodbhavaṃ |
J1: śiṣodravaṃ Ko2: śiṣodbhavaṃ 13
R: musukhodbhavam

126

R: amū A1: cūrṇavi^o A2, U: cūrṇaviḍaṃ
śreṣṭhaṃ B: cūrṇaṃ viḍaṃ śreṣṭhaṃ G,
R: cūrṇaṃ viḍaṃ śreṣṭhaṃ J1: cūrṇavidade
śreṣṭhaṃ Ko1: cūrṇā viḍe śreṣṭhaṃ
Ko2: cūrṇai₁ ḍaseṣṭhaṃ P: cūrṇaviḍe śreṣṭhaṃ
Pa: cūrṇaṃ viḍe śreṣṭe | Pa: sarva ra^o P: sa-
rbara^o B: melaka |91 J1: pūrvayogena Ko2: jā-
raet U: jāyētpūrvaprayogena A2: pūrba^o A1,
B, G, Pa, R: pūrva^o P: sarbayo^o Ko2: pūrva-
prayogena J1: jārayet -₁ maṇinama^o
A1: maṇa₁ nima^o A2: maṇirājasya J1: jāga-
raṇaṃ

pūrvaparasya saṃyogāt lokapālāya dāpayet|
tasya mūlaṃ phalaṃ grāhyaṃ nakṣatre yamadau vate |

A1, G, Ko1, P, Pa, U: pūrvāpa° J1: pūrvāpūra-
vasya Ko2: pūrvāmaparasa R: pūrvāparara
A2, B: pūrvāparasam° G: saṃyogād J1: sayo-
gān Ko1: saṃyo gē gā t Ko2: yogāt
Pa: saṃyot | R: saṃyogālokapālī yadā bhavet
Ko1: lokam pā° A1, P: lokampā° B: lokapālī
A2: lokam yāsī yadā bhavet G: lokapālī le yadā
bhavet|| Ko2, U: lokapālī yadā bhavet B: sadā
bhavet |92 J1: dāpaye₁ G: tadā J1: vatasya
A1: phaiṃlmūlaṃ Ko2: mūla G: mūlaphale
J1, U: mūlaphalaṃ G: grāhye Pa: grā-
hya|Lnakṣatra A1, A2, J1, Ko2, R, U: yama-
daivate B: yamadevate | P: yamadauvate
Pa: yamadaivatam ||

127

asya pūrvaprabhāvena padmarāgasya jāraṇam|
vārāratne mahādīṣṭhaṃ punaḥ pūrveṇa vāntike |

Ko2: yasya R: tasya Ko2: cūrṇampra° A1, A2,
B, G, J1, Ko1, P, Pa, R, U: cūrṇampra°
Ko2: °gasa Ko2: ja₁raṇam J1, Ko2, U: varā°
B: vāvārane G: vārāratnai R: vyacārante A2, G,
Pa: sahā° Ko2: sadādibhyaṃ R: mahādīṣṭham
U: sadādīṣṭham J1: puna Ko2: pūnām
R: puraḥ Pa, U: punaḥpū° B: cūrṇeṇa A2, G,
U: cāmṭike B: vaṃLtikaiḥ J1: vāntike Ko2: cā-
tikam 16 Pa: vāmṭikaiḥ | 21 R: vāntikaiḥ

128

ghoṣayitvā kutam pūrṇam mahānilarasaplutam|
tīvralolārasenaiva moddayitvā punaḥ punaḥ |

R: śeṣa° A2, G, U: śoṣa° Ko2: seṣa_itvā A1, A2,
B, G, J1, P, Pa, R: kṛtam Ko2: dae U: hṛtam
A1, A2, G, J1, Ko1, Ko2, P, Pa, R, U: cūrṇam
B: cūrṇa G: mahānilam ra° A2: mahānilam
ra° B: mahānilārasapluta ||94 Ko2: mahānila-
rasayūtam R: mahānilāraseplutam J1: °sa-
dbhutam B: tātra lo° Ko2: tāmmra₁lo° A2, G,
R, U: tāmrālo° R: soda° A2: moddayitvā G,
U: mardayitvā Ko2: marda_itvā Ko2: pūna
pūna 17 idranīlamahānilamaraktam ketakam
tathā yūṣmayamtreṇa madhya₁stham jārita-
vyam Pa: punaḥpunaḥ A1: om Ko2: pū-
naz || 18 R: punaḥ |₁ indranīlo R: add mahānī-
lam sankam tam kaitakam tathā ūṣmāyantra-
sya madhyastham jāritavyam prayatnataḥ

129

pāṭilānti saṃyogāt yadā kāle rajaḥśvalā |
tasyāḥ puṣparasenaiva kāryaṃ rakṣā yathocitā |

A2: yāditi° A1: pāṭiḥlānti B: pāṭiḥlānti G: kā-
kinīstrī Ko2: poṭiyāti Pa: pāṭilāyāti R: pāditiḥ |
U: pāṭiyāti Ko2, U: add ca R: add lāṭi
B: saṃyogā G: saṃyogo Ko2: saṃjogāt
R: maṃyogaṃ R: yodā A1, Ko1, P: kale
J1: kali R: kāla A1, A2, B, G, J1, Ko1, Ko2, P,
Pa, U: rajasvalā R: rajasvala A1, J1, P: tasyā
Ko2, U: tasthā R: rasya A2, Ko1, L: ta-
syāḥpuṣ° A2: kāryā B, G: kāyā Ko2, U: kārya
Pa: kārye R: kāya B: yathocitām |

130

kṣetrapālo dhanādhyakṣaḥ śivo viṣṇuḥ prajāpatiḥ |
mārttaḍaṃ yāvata bhūtvā lokapālāṣṭakaiḥ saha |

Pa: kṣatra° Ko2: ṣetra° R: kṣetrapālaṃ A1, B,
Ko1, P, Pa, U: dhanādhyakṣa J1: dhanā-
dhyakṣya Ko2: dhanādhyakṣo
R: gaṇādhyakṣaṃ J1: śivpo Ko2: sivo A1, B,
J1, Ko1, P, Pa, U: viṣṇu Ko2: viṣṇū
A2: biṣṇupra° A1, J1, Ko1, Ko2, P, R: prajā-
pati A1, Ko1, P, Pa, U: mārttaḍaṃ B: mā-
rttaḍa G: mārkāḍe J1, Ko2: mārttaḍa
R: māṇḍavya A2: mārttaḍapāvaka
A1: yāvamtā B: yācako G: yo₁vako
Ko2: pāvako R: yā...ko U: yāvako A1, Ko1,
Ko2: °ṣṭakai R: °kaissaha B: sahaḥ |

131

candanāgurudhūpaiś ca pūjayitvā prayatnataḥ |
namaskṛtya guruṃ devaṃ tato bhakṣen mahārasam |

A2: caṃdanā gu° Ko2: caṃdanāgūruṃdhu-
paiś R: °rudhupaiś J1: caḍaṃnāgaradhūpai-
śca Ko2: pūja_itvā Ko2: prayatnata J1: nama-
stubhya Ko2: namaskṛtaṃ Ko2: gūruṃ A1,
J1, Ko1, P: gurudevam Ko2: bhūkte U: bhu-
kte J1: bhuktenma° A1, B, L, P,
Pa: bhakṣenma° G: mahārasaḥ |

132

godohanamātraṃ tu mūrccitaḥ sādhaś carāḥ |
uttiṣṭhati na sandeho trinetrāś caturbhujāḥ |

J1: gohadona° R: godohanāmapātraṃ Ko2,
U: °nasya mātraṃ L: °na mātraṃ A2, B, Ko2,
U: mūrccito R: mūrkitasmādhaś U: sādha-
kottamaḥ | A1, J1, P: sādhaśvarāḥ A2, B,
Pa: sādhaśvarāḥ Ko1: sādhaśvrāḥ
Ko2: sādhaśkottama G, R: caraḥ U: om A2, B,
G, J1, Pa, R, U: uttiṣṭati Ko1: urttiṣṭati
Ko2: utiṣṭati A2: saṃdehos R: sandeha

133

gaṇanāthaḥ tathā siddhā cānye gaṇanāyakāḥ|
āgacchanti puras tasya siddhavidyādhārādayaḥ |

A2: triṇetraś J1: trinetrāśca Ko2, U: cite ta-
sya R: strinetraś A1, B, Pa, R: add ca A1: śca-
tu° G: caturānanah| | Ko2: caturbhūryaṃ 22

134

paśyanti bhuvanaṃ sarvaṃ vimānasthā mahāmune|
hāraḥ kaṇakarpūraiḥ kuṇḍalair mukuṭais tathā |

A1, B, J1, Ko1, Ko2, P, Pa: gaṇanātha
R: gaṇanāthastathā U: gaṇanāthastathā
Ko2: sthā₁ A2: siddhāye Ko2: sidhaṃ U: si-
ddhaḥ ye A1, B, G, J1, P, Pa, R: add ye
Ko2: vyayayāne R: vānye Ko2: gaṇanāthakā
Ko2, U: āgachati R: Lāgaśchanti A1, B, J1,
Ko1, P, Pa, U: puraṃ Ko2: pūraṃ
A2: puramṭasya L, R: purastasya J1: siddhivi°
A1: sidhaviṃdyā° Ko2: °daya 23

135

śaṅkhakālādanirghoṣai rasogīta vādibhiḥ|
puṣpamālāpatākābhiḥ kiṃkiṇārasaṃhitaiḥ |

Ko2: pasyamti A1, J1, Pa: bhavanaṃ Ko1,
P: bhavataṃ Ko2: bhūvanaṃ L: bhavataḥ A1,
B, G, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa, R: vimānastho
Ko2: vāṃmana₁sthā B: mahāmuni ||₁ G: ma-
hāmuniḥ|| Ko2: mahāmmūne Pa: mahāmu-
neh|₁₀ R: mahāmaniḥ Ko2: hāraka R: hāra-
kaṃ₁ A1, P: hārakaṃka° A2, B, U: hāra-
kaṃkaṇakeyūraiḥ Pa: hārakaṃkaṇakerpū-
raiḥ | G: kaṇakayūraiḥ Ko2: gaṇakampūrai
R: kaṇakeyūrai R: kkuṇḍalair J1,
P: kuṇḍalairmukuṭaistathā
Ko2: kuḍalemukuṭesthā 24 R: matkuṭaistathā
U: mukuṭaistathā||

A2: śaṅkhakāhalanirghoṣer B, R: śaṅkhakā-
halanirghoṣair G: śaṅkhakāhalanirghoṣaiḥ
Ko2: seṣekahālenirghoṣe asya U: śaṃsakāha-
lani₁rghoṣaiḥ asya Ko1: °lāhanirghoṣair
Pa: °lānirghoṣai| J1: °lāhani₁rghoṣairapsaro-
gīta A1: °lāhanirghoṣerapsaro gītavādibhiḥ
P: °lāhanirghoṣairapsarogītaLvādibhiḥ
A2: apsarogītā₁ G: apsarogīta R: apsarogīta-
vā° Ko1: ajharogītavā° B: apsarogītavā°
Ko2: ro gītavādanai₁ Pa: rapsaro gītavādibhi
11 U: ro gītavādinaiḥ|| A2: nāditaḥ J1: vādibhi
A2: puṣpamālāpatā° J1: puṣpamālāpatākā-

136

rave varatvaṃ prayacchanti yatra devo maheśvaraḥ |
kṛtāmjalipuṭā bhūtvā śivasyāgre vivasthitaḥ |

śrībhairavovāca |

137

sāhasraṃ duścaraṃ ghoraṃ adbhutaṃ ca kṛtaṃ mayā |
tvadbhaktiā tu hy ahaṃ tuṣṭo svacchandaprativāraḥ |

bhi Ko2: pūphamālāpatake G: °lāyatakābhiḥ
B, U: °tākaiś A1, Ko1, P: °kābhi B, Ko2,
U: add ca L: kiṃ kiṇā ra° A1: kikiranāra-
maṃḍitaiḥ 59 A2, R: kiṃ kiṇīravamaṃḍitaiḥ
B: kiṃki|nānavamaṃḍitaiḥ | G: kiṃ kiṇī ra-
tnamaṃḍitaiḥ | J1: kiṃ kiraṇārava-
maṃḍiḥ taiḥ Ko1: ki kiraṇā ravamaṃḍitaiḥ
Ko2: kiṃ kaṇi sūramaṃḍite 25 P: kikiranāra-
vamaṃḍitaiḥ Pa: kiṃkiṇī ravamaṃḍitaiḥ |
U: kiṃ kiṇī varamaṃḍitaiḥ |

A2: khe A1, G, J1, Ko1, P, Pa: khecaratvaṃ
B: khecarabaṃdhajevvīghraṃ Ko2: ṣecaratna
R: ravecaratvaṃ U: ṣacaratvaṃ A2: ca ḥ ralaṃ
A2: add vraje A2: chīgraṃ B: om G: vrajec chi-
ghraṃ Ko2: vrajedhijñam R: vraješchīghraṃ
U: vrajevighnaṃ Ko1: vyatra Ko2: yaṃtra
R: yadra J1: maheśvara Ko2: maheśvasvara
Ko2: kṛtāmjalipuṭo, U: kṛtāmjalipuṭo A1: °li
puṭā R: °lipaṭo A2, B, G, J1, P, Pa: °puṭo
Ko2: savasāgare A1, Ko1: vivasthita A2, B, G,
J1, R, U: vyavasthitaḥ Ko2: vīvasthītaṃ 26

A2, L

A1, J1, Ko1: sāhastam Ko2, U: sahasraṃ
P: sāhastamsam Pa: sāhasam R: moḥam
B: sohesaduḥkaraṃ A1, J1: duḥśvaraṃ
G: duḥkaraṃ Ko1, L: duḥścaraṃ Ko2: pūska-
raṃ P: duḥś caraṃ Pa: duḥkaraṃ R,
U: puṣkaraṃ A2: duḥkaraghoram J1: ghora
adbhutaṃ R: ghoramadbhutaṃ Ko2: yadbhū-
taṃ U: aḥ dbhūtaṃ Ko2: cekṣītaṃ
U: cekṣītaṃ A1: prayāṃ A2, B, G, Ko2, P, Pa,
R, U: tvayā J1: prayā-ḥ Ko1: payā A1: tva-
dbhadbhaktiā G: tvaḥ dbhaktiāham U: tva-
dbhaktiānu B, R: om Ko2: tū A2: tubhyam
P: tutuhyaham G, Ko2: om J1: hyadam L, Pa,
U: hyaham R: hyadyaḥ samtuṣṭa B: ayam G: ca
Ko2: sva ham A2, B, Pa: tuṣṭaḥ G: add smi
B: svachamdam pra° A1, P, Pa: svachamda

138

sādhu sādhu mahāprājña mama śukrasya sādhaḥ |
svarge tiṣṭha ciraṃ kālaṃ yāvac candrāṅkatārakam |

139

rudrakanyā viṣṇukanyā brahmakanyās tathaiva ca |
bhuktvā ca vipulān bhogān kalpanti muktibhājanaḥ |

140

iti śrī nāgārjunaviracite mahārara uktā khecarabandha samāptaḥ |

pra° R: svaśchandapratīcārahā A2, U: °ticā-
rakah G: °ticāraka | Ko2: °tikāraka 27

A1, B, Ko2: om R: om B: om Ko2: mähā°
B: om B: om G: samaḥ U: namāmy Ko2: na-
māmasyāś ca B: om U: asyaś G: śakrasyasā°
U: add ca B: om J1, Ko1, P: sādhaḥ Ko2: sā-
dhavā U: mādhavah || A1, R: svargre B: ... tva-
rye A2, G, Ko1, Pa, R: tiṣṭha J1: tiṣṭati
Ko2: tiṣṭe U: tiṣṭe Pa: ciraṃkālaṃ | J1: kāla
J1: yāvatiṣṭamti R: yāvaś A2, L: yāvaccamdrā°
Ko2: yācamdrā'rkatāraka 28, A1, Ko1, P: add
tiṣṭha R: candrāṅkatārakah J1: camdrākītāra-
kah A1: °rakah 62

A2: rudrakanyā Ko2: rudrakamnyā U: ru-
drakamnyā R: rudrakanyāvi° A2: viṣṇukanyā
Ko1: viśukanyā Ko2: viśukamnyā P: vi-
śruṣṇukanyā U: viṣṇukamnyā A2: vrahma-
kamnyā B, J1, Pa: brahmakanyā Ko2, R: vrah-
makanyā P, U: brahmakanyāstathaiva
Pa: stathaiva A1, B, Pa: bhuktā J1, P, U: bhuk-
ttkā Ko2: bhuktvā A2, U: svavi° Ko2: scavipū-
lā A1, A2, B, J1, Ko1, P, R, U: kalpāṃte G: ka-
syāṃte Ko2: kamnyāte Pa: kalpāṃtam
B: bhukti° A1: muktabhājana 63 A2: mukti-
bhāgjanaḥ 92 Ko2: muktibhājanam 29
J1: °jana P, Pa, U: °janam

A2 Ko2: iti G: Ko2, R, U: om Pa: śrīnāgārjune
vi° L: śrīnāgārjunavi° Ko1: śrīnāgārjuno, vi°
A1, J1, P: śrīnāgārjuno vi° B: śrīnāgārju-
nahṛdayāsthāṃ phaṭ || U: nāgārjunahṛdayā-
straṃ Ko2: °na R: °naviraci °te
G: °nahṛdayāstrephaṭ || L Ko2: add sadayāstra
ṣaṭu R: add rasaratnākare traipaṭā J1, Ko2,
R: mahārasa Pa: mahārasam
U: ṣaṭ || māhā, L... | rasa B: mahārasa uktamṛta
P: mahā_ra sauktā Ko2: utkrṣṭa R: ukta
U: utkrṣṭa ta R: add mṛta P: ṣekhe° Ko1,

L: ṣeca° Ko2, U: ṣecara Pa: °baṃdhaḥ R: °va-
 ndhaṃ J1: °dhaLmāsa B: °dhasamāptami-
 ti ||ṭha|| Ko2: add vo ṣaṭ U: add vau ṣaṭ|| iti
 J1: saptamodhyāyaḥ 7 Ko2: smāptaṃ
 R: masamāptamiti ||

[Jalūkādirasabandhana] 141

rase vīrye vipāke ca śuddhaṃ tadvindusūtakam |
 tena janmajarāvyaḍhim harate sūtakam bhuvī |

A2: add iti nāgārijjunahṛdayā, stramphahāma-
 hārāsa uktaḥ mṛtakhecaratvraṃdhaḥ samā-
 ptam iti R: rasavīryaṃ U: rasavīryavi°
 Ko2: om Pa: vīrye B: sudhā G: sudhāvad J1,
 Pa: śruddhaṃ R: śuddhā U: sudhāvadbimdu°
 A2: sudhāvaddhimdu° Pa: tadbimdu° J1: tā-
 rddhaṃ du° G: vimdu° P: tadvimdu sū° B: va-
 dhidhasūtakaḥ | R: va, viṭasūtakaḥ Pa: °rā vā
 vyā, dhi A1, B, J1, Ko1, P, R, U: °vyādhi
 A2: °vyādhai A2: sūtako B: sūtaka

142

khoṭaṃ padaṃ jalūkā ca bhasmaṃ caiva caturthakam |
 pañcamo mūrtibaddhaś ca mūrccitaḥ ṣaṣṭamo mataḥ |

A2: ṣoṭaṃ R: khoṭa U: ṣaṭaṃ Ko2: om A2,
 U: paṭaṃ B: badhaṃ G: ghaṭaṃ R: vandhaṃ
 J1: padaja° R: jalūkam G: vā A2, B, R, U: bha-
 sma J1: bhaśma B: caturtha|ka | A2, B,
 G: paṃcamaṃ R: paṃca U: paṃca saṃmū-
 rrtibaṃdhaṃ A2, B: mūrtivaddhaṃ G: mūrti-
 baddhaṃ R: saṃmūrtivaddhaṃ J1: mūrttiba-
 ddhaśca G: add ca ṣaṣṭaś R: om U: caṃ
 A2: mūrccitaṃ G: mūrtito J1: mūrbitaḥ
 R: mūrccitaḥ G: saktito A2: ṣaṣṭamaṃ G, R: om
 A2: viduḥ 94

143

bandhaḥ ṣaḍvidhaḥ jñeyo saptamo'mṛtasūtakaḥ |
 ādratvaṃ ca ghanatvaṃ ca ghanatvaṃ ca cāpalyaṃ kuru |

A1, Ko1: baṃdha B, Pa, U: baṃdhastu
 J1: vaṃdha R: vandhastu P: baṃ, dhaśa°
 Ko2: om A2, G: tu J1: ṣaḍvidha
 Ko1: ṣaḍvimdhaḥ, R: ṣaḍvidhe B, G, Pa: jñe-
 yaḥ L: seyo A2: jñeysaptamo mṛ°
 R: jñeyasmaptamo mūsūtakaḥ A1, B, J1,
 Ko1, P: saptamo mṛ° Pa: saptamo mṛtasūta-
 kaḥ | A1: ādraṃtvaṃ B, Ko1, P: ādratvaṃ
 Pa: adratvaṃ R: ardanam U: ādrakatvaṃ A1,
 R: om A2, G, U: om A2, G: om B, J1, Pa: om
 A2, G: om Ko1, P: vāpalyaṃ L: vāyapyaṃ

144

tejamāyasyaitāni na daśetetaṃ vidyādbhasmasūtakaṃ |
nānāvārṇa bhavet sūtaṃ vihāya ghanacāpalam |

A2: gurutejasī 95 B, G: gurutejasaḥ R: guru
U: gurutejasam || A1, J1: tejasā P: add tejamā
Pa, R: tejasah

A1, A2, B, G, J1, P, Pa, R, U: om tejamā°
Ko2: om A1: tadasetetaṃ A2, R, U: dṛśyamte
taṃ G: daśyamte taṃ J1: darśamte_na
Ko1: daśettenaṃ P: daśetenaṃ Pa: dṛsāmte |
taṃ | B: dṛśyamte tavidyānmṛtasū°
U: viṃdyānmṛtasū° R: vidyādgurusū° J1: vi-
dyādbhasmasū° G: vidyānmṛtasū°
A2: viṃdyānmṛtatakam Ko1: °takamḥ B, Pa,
R, U: nānāvārṇam A2: °rṇabhavet L: °rṇabha-
vetsūtaṃ A1, J1, P, Pa, R, U: bhavetsūtaṃ
Ko1: ghanam cāpalam J1: °pala

145

lakṣaṇam dṛśyate yasya mūrccitaṃ taṃ vadanti hi |
gurutvam aruṇatvam ca tejasā sūryasannibham |

A1 U: lakṣaṇa Ko2: om G: tasya Ko1, P: mū-
rcchita J1: ta R: varunti J1, L, P, Pa, R: guru-
tvamaru° G: asukvatvam R: vā Pa: tedasā
R: tejo U: tejam A2: tejo, bhāskarasannibham
97 B: tejabhāskarasannibham | G: tejobhīva-
karasamanvitaṃ | | J1: svarṇasannibham
Ko1, Pa: sūryasannibham R, U: bhāskarasa-
nnibham

146

śikhimadhye dhruvam tiṣṭhet baddhasūtasya lakṣaṇam |
kṛṣṇam śvetam tathā pītam nilam vā bhasma sannibham |

A1, A2, Ko1, L: śiṣimadhye J1: śiṣi, madhya P,
Pa: śiṣi madhye U: śiṣimadhyam G, Ko2: om
A1: bhuvam A2: kravam Ko1: dhuvam R: kra-
tam U: dhavam A2, B, J1, Ko1, P: tiṣṭhet
U: tiṣṭhetbamdha° R: tiṣṭhetvaddhasūtaka
A1: vadha° B: bamdhasūtakala° A2: °taka-
lakṣaṇam J1: nānāvārṇata R: kṛṣṇa A1, Ko1,
P, Pa: svetaṃ J1: bhāsvacham J1: ghṛtam
Pa: tathāpītam | J1: yojñau A2, B, J1, U: om
A2: bhasmanaḥ B: bhasmani J1: om R: bha-
mma A1, Pa: bhasmasannibham J1: jalū-
ka, vat U: nisannibham ||

147

capalatvam yadā naṣṭam bhasmasūtasya lakṣaṇam |

J1, Ko2, R: om U: °taka B: nānā varṇam

nānāvarṇaṃ tathā svinnaṃ ghr̥taṃ yo'gnau jalūkavat |

G: vardhate A2: yadā U: yathā G: sūtakaṃ A1,
P, Pa: svachaṃ A2: svādhrtatejo B, Ko1,
U: svasthaṃ A2: add jalū₁kavat A2: varddhate
sūtakaṃ B, Pa: ghr̥te G: yaś U: dh̥rte A2: ya-
sya B: yone G: ca Ko1: yoṃ gnau U: tejo
A2: jalūkābaddha--lakṣaṇaṃ 99 G: jalūkāva-
ddhalakṣaṇaṃ||₁

148

varddhate sūtakaṃ yac ca jalūkābaddhalakṣaṇaṃ |
śvetaṃ pītaṃ gurutvaṃ ca mṛdusikyakasannibhaṃ |

G: nānāvarṇaṃ tathā Pa: vardhamte A2: om
Ko2, R: om G: svacchaṃ G: dh̥rti A1, L, P: ya-
cca J1: yacha G: om A1: jaṃlū° P: jalūkāva-
ddha° G: tejājalūkavat || B: °ddha la|₁ |
Pa: °laṇaṃ | 24 A1, J1, Ko1, P: svetaṃ
B: sveta Pa: svetaṃ₁ taṃ G, J1: pīta Pa: guru-
tva G: mṛdusikthaka° U: mṛdu₁sithaka°
A2: mṛdumsikthaka° B: mṛdusikthasaṃni-
bhaṃ ||8 J1: mṛdusi₁kthaka sannibhaṃ
Pa: mṛdusite ca saṃnibhaṃ | A1,
Ko1: °kasaṃnibhaṃ

149

agnimadhye yadā tiṣṭhet pāṭabandhasya lakṣaṇaṃ |
kukkuṭāṃḍanibhaṃ sūtaṃ lohavedhī bhaved yadā |

Ko2: om A1: vyadā L: yadāti° A2: yadātiṣṭet B,
Pa, U: tiṣṭe Ko1, R: tiṣṭet J1: tiṣṭetpāṭa°
A1: tiṣṭetpāṭavaibaṃ° P: tiṣṭetpāṭavaṃdhasya
U: padabaṃ° R: saṭṭavan° Pa: pāṭubaṃ°
A2: sadr₁vaṃ° B: paṭṭabadhasya
Ko1: pāṭavaṃdhasya B, Pa, U: kurkuṭāṃ°
P: kukkuṭāṃ° A1: kukkuṭāṃḍābhanibhaṃ
R: kukkuṭāṃḍānibhaṃ J1: kurkuṭāṃ duni-
bhasū₁taṃ B: sūta A2: lavaṇabedhi
B: lavaṇavedhī G: lavaṇābhaṃ yadā
R: laṇobhedī U: lavaṇa bhedi₁Lbha° A1: add
bhāvadhinai 9 Ko1, P: bhaved J1: bhavedyadā
G: om A2: add āva₁rttitaḥ punas tadvat
khoṭobaddharasākṛtiḥ 101

150

āvarttitaṃ punas tadvat ṣoṭavaddharasākṛtiḥ |

A2 J1: āvarttitaṃ R: ā₁vantitaṃ U: āvarttitaḥ
Ko2: om R: puna J1, L, Pa: punastadvat
B: om R: yadvat P, Pa: ṣoṭabaddha°
G: khoṭabaddha° U: ṣoṭabaṃdho ra°
R: koṭidhā ca ra° B: ṣo₁ra° A1: ṣoṭabadhara-

athavā

151

nnede | snigdham mṛdum caiva śikhinā drāvito dravet|
akṣayam kaṭhinam śvetam ṣoṭabaddhasya lakṣanam |

152

[London] ṣoṭādayeṣu ye pañca vihāya jalūkākṛtiḥ|
hatāgnau dhāmitam tiṣṭhet na tiṣṭhed ekamūrchitaḥ |

153

taruṇādityasaṅkāśo nānāvārṇavicakṣaṇaḥ|
vedhayed dehalohāni rañjito rasabhairavaḥ |

sākṛti Ko1: ṣoṭavad vara sā kṛtiḥ J1: °kṛti
L: add athavānnede |

A2, G, Ko2, L

A2: add athavā A1, J1, Ko1, P, Pa, U: chede
A2, B: svede G: bede L: om R: svedais
Ko2: om J1, Ko1: sigdham R: svinnam
J1: mṛdu R: mṛdam U: śiṣinā A1: drāvato
J1: drāvitā A1: add da R, U: bhavet B: akṣaya
R: a ḷkṣayam A2: kiṭhinam A1: eḷśvatam
G: śvete J1, Ko1, P, Pa: svetam A2: khotā°
R: khaṭova° G: khotavaddhasya Ko1: ṣoṭava-
dvasya U: ṣoṭabamdhasya B: lakṣaṇa
R: lakṣam

G: add kukkuṭamdanibham A1, B, J1, Ko1, L,
P, Pa, U: om A2: khotādeyās tu R: khotās ca
ye G: om Ko2: om A1: ṣodāda° B: ṣoṭādayasu
J1: ṣodādayesu Pa: ṣoṭādayaḥ U: ṣoṭādayastu
Ko1: °yesu R: add ca Pa: śrutāḥ B, R, U: jalu-
kā° A2: jalukā kṛtiḥ ḷ G: sūtam Ko1: jalūkāL
kṛti L: jalūkā kṛtiḥ| A1, J1, P, Pa: °kṛti A2, Pa,
U: haṭhāgnau R: haṭhāgro J1: hagasaudhmā-
pitaḥ A2, B: dhāmitāḥ G: dhāmita santi
R: dhāmiḷ tasmanti U: dhamitāssamti A2,
B: samti J1, P: tiṣṭet A2, B, P: tiṣṭed
J1: tiṣṭedeka° A1: tiṣṭedeka mūrchitaḥ ḷ L,
Pa: tiṣṭhedeka mūrchitaḥ R: tiṣṭedeke mū-
rchitaḥ U: viṣṭedeka mūrchitaḥ|| G: ekamūr-
ti-
taḥ| | Ko1: eka mūrchitaḥ

J1: taruṇādityasaṅkāśam R: °dirvyasaṅkāśo
G: lavaṇādityasaṅkāśonānāvārṇavi° U: °tya
saṅkāśam nānāvārṇā vicakṣaṇaḥ|| Ko2: om
Pa: nānāvārṇe vi° A2: nānā--barṇe vi° B: nā-
nāvārṇo vi° A1, Ko1, P: °kṣaṇa A2: bedheṣu
B: vedhe G, U: vedheṣu R: vadheṣu J1: vedha-
ye-ḷ dde ha° A1, L: vedhayeddeha° A2, G,
R: lohadeheṣu B: lohadehe U: saha loheṣuḷ

154

[London] śodhanaṃ sūtakasyādaḥ grāsamānamataḥ param |
jāraṇaṃ tv abhṛakādīnāṃ sarvasattvamataḥ param |

B: puram̐ jitaḥ R: raṃji₁te A2: raṃjitasūtala-
kśaṇam̐ 1 104 B, R, U: sūtalakṣaṇam̐ G: śubha-
lakṣaṇaḥ |

A1, A2, B, G, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa, R, U: om
Ko2: om A1: grāmamā° G: grāsamāno yataḥ
R: °nasataḥ U: grāsanaṃ J1: jā-₁raṇatva
bhra° R: jāraṇamabhrakasyāpi B, G, U: om
A1, L, P, Pa: tvabhra° A2: cābhrakasyā₁pi B,
U: abhrakasyāpi G: abhrakasyādhīnāṃ
J1: saṃrva satvaṃ mataḥ Ko1: sarvasattvam
ataḥ U: °taḥpa₁raṃ||

155

garbhavādyadutiḥ paścāt suvarṇaṃ tadanantaram |
dīvyośadhipuṭaṃ paścāt ratnabandhamataḥ param |

A1: garbhabāhyadutiḥ A2: garbhavāhyadrutau
G: garbhavahnidutau J1: garbhavāhyaṃ dutiḥ
Pa: garbhabāhyadrutiḥ R: gavāhyaśrutaḥ
U: garbhabāhyarutau P: °duniḥ B: garbha-
vāpa° Ko2: om R: tadarattaram B, Ko1, R: di-
vyo° A2, G: dīvyauśadhi° A1, J1: dīvyośadhi-
puṭaṃ Pa: dīvyośadhipuṭaṃ U: dīvyauśadhi-
puṭaṃ P: °dhi puṭaṃ R: paścādrandrava-
ndhasataḥ Ko1: ratnabandham̐ ataḥ

156

rañjanaṃ ca tataḥ proktaṃ sārāṇāsyānusārāṇā |
tato'pi kāraṇe deyaṃ sūtakasya vicakṣaṇe |

Ko2: om A1, Ko1, P: tata J1: prokta A1, A2,
B: sārāṇasyā° G: sārāṇā cānu° J1: spā-
raṇāspānu₁ sārāṇāḥ R: māraṇamyānuś ca
māraṇā U: sārāṇaṃ sānuśārāṇaṃ|| A2, G: tato
pi U: tatoṃ'daṃ A2, B, U: krāmaṇaṃ G: kra-
mitaṃ R: krāmāṇaṃ Pa: jñeyaṃ | J1: sūtake-
spa A1, Pa: vicakṣaṇaiḥ A2: bicakṣa₁ṇaiḥ 107
B: vicakṣa₁ḥ | G, R, U: vicakṣaṇaḥ J1: ci-
cakṣaṇaiḥ

157

[London] eṇaṃ kramaṃ tu yo vetti tasya siddhiḥ na saṃśayaḥ |
vedhakraṃmaṃ vijānāti dehalohe rasāyane |

A1, A2, B, G, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa, R, U: om
Ko2: om A2, G: imaṃ B: eṣa Ko1: ena R: etat
U: eṣaḥ J1: karma B: sidhi R: middhi A1, J1,
P, Pa: siddhirna R: nna J1: śaṃśayaḥ R: add
dehe tu paṃcaratnāni A2: vedhakramaṃ
B: yokrāmaṃ G: vedhaṃ kramaṃ J1: vedha-

158

tasya janmajarāvyādhir naśyante nātra saṃśayaḥ |
atraiva pañcaratnāni nāgavaṅgo tathāyasaṃ |

159

krāmaṇaṃ rasarājasya auṣadhān samavāpayet
auṣadhaiḥ kramate sūto yogamuktikrameṇa hi |

160

[London] kramate vyādhisandhātaṃ grasate duṣṭarogakān |
tasmāt tatkarmasaṃjñā yato vaidyair upācayet |

karma P: vedhakrāmmaṃ Pa: vedhakāmaṃ
R: nāgavaṅgaṃ tathā yamau yathokramaṃ
U: ||||vedhaḥ krāmaṃ A2: na jā° J1: vijānīyāt
Ko1, P: vijānāni A1, A2, B, J1, P, Pa, U: dehe
lohe R: dehe R: add loho R: marāyane |

Ko2: om L: °rākhyādhiḥ A1, B, Ko1, P,
U: °vyādhi R: °vyādhinnaśyate B, J1, Pa: na-
śyate U: naśyete A2, L: nātrasaṃ° J1: śamsaya
atraiva A2, B, U: dehe tu A2, B, U: om G: dehe
R: om U: °ni|nāgaṃ baṅgaṃ A1: nāgavaṃto
A2, G: nāgaṃ vaṅgaṃ B: nāgavaṅgaṃ
J1: nāgavaṅgo Pa: nāgavaṅgau B: tathā-
nyamet | G: tathā rase|| J1: tathāyasaḥ
Ko1: tathāyasaṃ U: tathāyase||

J1: kaḥ rmaṇaṃ R: kramaṇaṃ Ko2: om B: °ja-
sya dauṣadhī J1: °jasya uṣadhāt Pa: °jasya |
aṣadhāt R: °jamyasya doṣadhāt U: °jasya
oṣadhām A1, A2, G, Ko1, P: °dhāt R: add sa-
rvam A2, B: sarvamāyase G: sarvam āyase ||
R: āyame U: sarvamāyayau|| B, Pa: aṣadhaiḥ
U: oṣadhaiḥ A1, B, G, Pa: krāmate J1: krā-
mpate Ko1, P: krāmata L: krāmataḥ
U: kraṃmate R, U: sūtaṃ B: vyādhisamghāta-
grasate A2, U: yogayukti° G: yogayuktakra°
A1, P, Pa: °kti krameṇa R: om B: add mayā
B: | t

A1, A2, G, J1, Ko1, L, P, Pa, U: om R: om
B: om Ko2: om A1, A2, G, J1, Ko1, P, Pa,
U: vyādhisamghātaṃ R: vyādhisamghātaṃ
R: add ca J1: trasate R: naśyati A2,
R: duṣṭamāmayān G: duṣṭam J1: duṣṭate
rākān U: duṣṭamāyāt|| G: add āyase| B, Ko1,
P: tasmā U: bhasma Pa: tasmāttatka° R: tta-
smātkrāmaṇaṃ jñātvā L: tat karma° A1: ka-
rma° A2, G, U: tatkrāmaṇaṃ jñātvā B: krā-
maṇaṃ jñātvā J1: karmasaṃjñāya
Ko1: °jñāya to A2, B, G, J1, R, U: tato

161

krāmaṇena vinā sūto na kramen naiva vindhati |
dehalohāmayān sarvān vṛthā syāt kevalaśramaḥ |

A1: vedhaidyair A2: baidya B, R: vaidya G: ve-
dhair Ko1: veerror for te vai in pṛṣṭhamā-
tra?chair Pa: vidyair J1: vaidyarūpācarat
P: vedyairupācaret A1: ū pācayeret 19 A2, B,
G, Ko1, Pa, R, U: upācaret

J1: kārmaṇenam Ko2: om G: visūtaṃ A2, R,
U: sūtaṃ B: sūta R: om B: krāma G, R: kra-
meṇa A1: krametvaiva L: krametvaivaṃ
P: kramenvaiva Pa: kramātvaiva A2, R, U: na
ca B: na G: hi J1: vevaṃ Ko1: vaiva G: vidhya-
ti | J1: vidhati R: vindati U: dehe lo° Pa,
R: dehalohama° B: dehalohām Ko1: °yāt
A1: °yānsarvān P: °yātsarvān B: add atho
R: sarvāṃ U: savani P: syātkeva° Pa: syātkeva-
la śramaḥ | J1: kova° A1: kevala śramaḥ 20
A2: kepalaśramaḥ 1 112 B: kevala 1 laḥ śra-
maḥ ||20 G: kevale bhramaḥ || 1 L: kevalaṃ śra-
maḥ | R: kevala śramaḥsaḥ

162

yasya yogasya yo yogas tenaiva saha yojayet |
rasendro harate vyādhiṃ narakuṃjaravyādhinām |

Ko2: om B, R, U: rogasya G: rāgasya A2: yaṃ
U: yad B: yadyoga R: yadyogaṃ A2: yogaṃ
Pa: yoga | U: योग्याṃ J1, P: yogastenaiva
Pa: stenaiva R: sa 1 U: rasa U: rasendrau
J1: raseṃdrāha° A1, J1, Ko1, P, U: vyādhi
G: vyāṃdhiṃ B: naraḥ kuṃjaravājinām ||21
R: nagraḥktaṃjara vājinām U: narāṇāṃ vāji-
kuṃjaraiḥ || 1 || A2: °ra--bājinām 113 G: °ravāji-
nām | |

163

vyādhim ādau parīkṣeta tato dadyāc ca bheṣajam |
sūtakena samāyuktaṃ yojayec ca bhiṣagvaraḥ |

G: add śriḥ U: vidhim P, R: vyādhimādau
Ko2: om A1: parikṣetaṃ A2: parikṣyeta
J1: parikṣeL Ko1: parikṣet P, Pa: parikṣeta
A1, J1, L: dadyā R: rudyāś P: dadyāvabhe° A1,
L: va Ko1: om J1: bheṣaja Pa: bheṣajam |
L: sūvakena P: sūcakena R: mūtakena R: sa-
māyukto R: yojayes J1, P: yojayecca B,
J1: bhiṣagvara

164

[London] śrīmannāgārjunaviracite rasendramaṅgale guṭikāsatvadrutijālū-
kājāraṇādirasabandhanaṃ nāma caturtho'dhyāyaḥ |

A1, A2, B, G, J1, Pa, R, U: iti Ko1, L, P: om
Ko2: om A2: śrīśrī° R: om śrīman° P, U: śrīnā°
Ko1: śrīmannāgārjunavi° A1: śrīmannā-
gāmṛjuno vi° B: śrīnāgārjunaviracita R: rasa-
ratnākare U: guṭikāsatvadrutijālū° Pa: guṭikā-
tve drutijālū° L: guṭikātvedutijālū° P: guṭikā-
tve dutijālū° A2: guṭikāsatvahutijālū°
A1: guṭikātvādutijālū° Ko1: guṭikātvedutijālū-
kājāraṇādirasabaṃdha B: °tvadutijālūkājā-
raṇādirasabaṃdhano R: °tva...ti_L jalūkājā-
raṇādiramasavandhako G: °dha_Lno
J1: guṭikātvedutijālūkājāraṇādirasavaṃdha-
naṃ_L nāma A2, G, U: caturtho dhyāyaḥ
J1: caturppo dhyāyaḥ B: add samāptaḥ |||